

— MASTER THESIS —

**Modelling and implementation of a real-time flexible aircraft simulation
environment with animation of flight path, attitude and airframe
deformation**

Author: Zeinab Aboelmagd Ahmed Eltaher Ahmed
Matrikel-Nr.: 376976

Reviewers: Prof. Dr.-Ing. Flávio Silvestre
Dr. Pedro J. González
Ralf Senger Franco M. Sc.

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Abstract

This thesis presents the development and implementation of a real-time animation tool designed to visualise the deformation of flexible aircraft. The primary objectives are to create a robust framework that accurately represents the deformation of the wing, the horizontal tail, and the vertical tail and to evaluate the performance of the tool under various simulated conditions. The demonstrator aircraft used for this thesis is the UP-Wing aircraft model. This aircraft is the DLR F-25 research aircraft with modified wing parameters. The DLR F-25 is similar to the Airbus A321 neo but with a high aspect ratio. The methodology used to develop this animation tool consists of three main steps. First, the aeroelastic flight dynamics model was calculated and simulated using MATLAB/Simulink. Then, the 3-D model was animated in X-Plane. Finally, a plugin was implemented to facilitate the communication between Simulink and X-Plane. The aeroelastic flight dynamics model included the calculation of rigid body stability derivatives using AVL, the extraction of eigenvalues and eigenvectors from NASTRAN, and the simulation of the flexible flight dynamics model in Simulink. Furthermore, the aeroelastic flight dynamics model included two aerodynamic approaches: quasi-steady and unsteady. However, the animation tool was only applied to the quasi-steady aerodynamic simulations due to the high processing time of the unsteady model, which made real-time animation impractical. In addition, for the animation process in X-Plane, an extensively modified 3-D model of an Airbus A320 was used. The modifications were performed using Blender and it included rigging and animating of the 3-D model. Subsequently, the aircraft was painted using ArmorPaint software. In a further step, a custom plugin was implemented in C++ to disable the X-Plane physics engine and facilitate data transfer from Simulink. Then, the performance of the animation tool was investigated. In this regard, time domain simulations were conducted for both longitudinal and lateral motions of the aircraft, using different input scenarios to analyse the dynamic response and structural behaviour. The investigation revealed that the developed animation tool successfully displayed the real-time animation of the aircraft's structural response. The performance of the tool was verified by comparing the X-Plane animation results with the MATLAB/Simulink plots, ensuring the reliability of the data transfer and animation accuracy. This real-time animation tool for flexible aircraft deformations has significant applications in the aircraft design phase, educational purposes, and virtual flight testing, improving both cost-reduction and safety. In addition, the tool can be applied to any aircraft model.

Zusammenfassung

In der vorliegenden Arbeit wird ein Echtzeitsimulator zur Visualisierung der Verformung von flexiblen Flugzeugen entwickelt und implementiert. Dabei soll der Simulator insbesondere die Verformung der Flügel, des Höhenleitwerks und des Seitenleitwerks abbilden. Zur Bewertung des Animationstools werden anschließend mehrere Simulationen unter verschiedenen Bedingungen mit dem UP-Wing Flugzeugmodell durchgeführt. Das UP-Wing Flugzeug entspricht dem DLR-F25 Forschungsflugzeug, einem Airbus A321 neo mit modifizierten Flügelparametern und einer im Vergleich zum Originalmodell erhöhten Flügelstreckung. Zur Entwicklung des Animationstools wurden die folgenden drei Schritte durchgeführt: Als erstes wurde das aeroelastische Flugdynamikmodell mit MATLAB/Simulink entwickelt und berechnet. Dann wurde das 3D-Modell in X-Plane animiert. Zum Abschluss wurde ein Plug-in erstellt, welches die Kommunikation zwischen dem MATLAB/Simulink Programm und X-plane ermöglicht. Für das aeroelastische Flugdynamikmodell wurden die Stabilitätsderivative des starren Körpers mittels AVL berechnet und die Eigenwerte und -vektoren aus der Software NASTRAN extrahiert. Dabei wurde das aeroelastische Flugdynamikmodell so entwickelt, dass sowohl quasi-stationäre als auch instationäre Aerodynamikmodelle berechnet werden können. Auf Grund von langen Berechnungszeiten für den instationären Fall, wurde das Animationstool in der vorliegenden Arbeit jedoch nur für das quasi-stationäre Modell verwendet. Zur Erstellung der Animation in X-Plane wurde zunächst ein Airbus A320 3-D Modell in Blender modifiziert und anschließend animiert. Weiterhin wurde das 3-D Modell mithilfe von ArmorPaint bemalt. Das Plug-in für die Kommunikation zwischen X-Plane und MATLAB/Simulink wurde in C++ implementiert. Dieses deaktiviert die X-Plane-Physik-Engine und ermöglicht die Datenübertragung von Simulink. Zum Abschluss der vorliegenden Arbeit werden Beispielsimulationen für die Längs- und Seitenbewegungen mit verschiedenen Eingangswerten durchgeführt, um das entwickelte Animationstool zu bewerten. Dabei werden insbesondere die dynamische Reaktion und das strukturelle Verhalten untersucht. Die X-Plane-Animationsergebnisse werden grafisch mit den Berechnungen des MATLAB/Simulink-Programms verglichen. Dieser Vergleich zeigt, dass das Animationstool die strukturelle Reaktion des Flugzeugs in Echtzeit erfolgreich abbilden kann. Außerdem wurden die Zuverlässigkeit der Datenübertragung und die Genauigkeit der Animation sichergestellt. Das Echtzeit-Animationstool für flexible Flugzeuge kann in der Flugzeugentwurfphase, für Bildungszwecke und für virtuelle Flugversuche angewendet werden. Folglich kann das Animationstool zur Kostenreduktion und zur Erhöhung der Sicherheit beitragen. Darüber hinaus lässt sich das Animationstool auf jedes Flugzeugmodell anwenden.

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Nomenclature

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AE	Aeroelastic
AVL	Athena Vortex Lattice
BRF	Body Reference Frame
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CG	Centre of Gravity
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
DOF	Degree of Freedom
DR	Dutch roll Mode
EOM	Equations of Motion
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
GBRF	Global Body Reference Frame
GVTs	Ground Vibration Tests
HAR	High Aspect Ratio
HE	Horizontal Empennage
HIL	Hardware in the Loop
IRF	Inertial Reference Frame
ITA	Aeronautics Institute of Technology
MAC	Modal Assurance Criteria
MIST	Modal Identification Software Toolbox
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
NED	North East Down Coordinate System
OpenVSP	Open Vehicle Sketch Pad

PBR Physically-Based Rendering

PH Phugoid Mode

QS Quasi-Steady

RB Rigid Body

SDK Software Developers Kit

SIL Simulation in the Loop

SP Short period Mode

S Spiral Mode

TCP Transmission Control Protocol

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

UDP User Datagram Protocol

US Unsteady

VE Vertical Empennage

VLM Vortex Lattice Method

Greek Symbols

α	Angle of Attack	rad
α_T	Engine Installation Angle	rad
β	Sideslip Angle	rad
δ_a	Aileron Deflection	rad
δ_e	Elevator Deflection	rad
δ_r	Rudder Deflection	rad
δ_T	Thrust Ratio	
δ_t	Thrust	N
η_i	Modal Amplitude	
Γ	Structural Dissipation	
γ	Torsion Deformation	m

λ_1	First Aerodynamic Lag State	
λ_2	Second Aerodynamic Lag State	
μ_{ii}	Generalised Mass Matrix	
ω	Angular Velocity	rad s^{-1}
ω_n	Undamped Natural Frequency	s^{-1}
ϕ	Bank Angle	rad
ψ	Heading Angle	rad
ρ	Air Density	kg m^{-3}
θ	Pitch Angle	rad
φ	Twist Angle	rad
ξ_i	Generalised Modal Damping	

Latin Symbols

ω_K	Absolute Angular Velocity	rad s^{-1}
$\underline{\underline{A}}$	System Matrix	
$\underline{\underline{B}}$	Input Matrix	
$\underline{\underline{C}}$	Output Matrix	
$\underline{\underline{D}}$	Feedthrough Matrix	
D	Drag	N
D	Structural Damping	
F	Forces acting on the Aircraft	N
g	Gravitational Acceleration	m s^{-2}
H	Altitude	m
h	Angular Momentum	$\text{kg m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
J	Inertia Tensor	$\text{kg m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$
L	Lagrange Matrix	
L	Lift Force	N

L	Roll Moment	Nm
M	Pitch Moment	Nm
M	Sum of Moments around the Aircraft	Nm
m	Aircraft Mass	kg
N	Yaw Moment	Nm
p	Linear Momentum	kg m s^{-1}
p	Roll Rate	rad s^{-1}
p_K	Absolute Angular Velocity in x-direction (Roll Rate)	rad s^{-1}
q	Generalised Coordinate	
q	Pitch Rate	rad s^{-1}
Q_k	Generalised Loads	
q_K	Absolute Angular Velocity in y-direction (Pitch Rate)	rad s^{-1}
r	Yaw Rate	rad s^{-1}
R^A	Aerodynamic Forces	N
r_K	Absolute Angular Velocity in z-direction (Yaw Rate)	rad s^{-1}
T	Kinetic Energy	$\text{kg m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$
T	Propulsive Forces	N
t	Time	s
T_{be}	Transformation Matrix from Earth Frame to Body Frame	
U	Input/Control vector	
U	Potential Energy	$\text{kg m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$
u	Aircraft Velocity Component with respect to Air in x-axis	m s^{-1}
u_K	Absolute Aircraft Velocity Component in x-axis	m s^{-1}
u_w	Wind Velocity Component in x-axis	m s^{-1}
V	Aircraft Velocity with respect to Air	m s^{-1}
v	Aircraft Velocity Component with respect to Air in y-axis	m s^{-1}

V_K	Absolute Aircraft Velocity	m s^{-1}
v_K	Absolute Aircraft Velocity Component in y-axis	m s^{-1}
V_w	Wind Velocity	m s^{-1}
v_w	Wind Velocity Component in y-axis	m s^{-1}
W	Aircraft Weight	N
w	Aircraft Velocity Component with respect to Air in z-axis	m s^{-1}
w_K	Absolute Aircraft Velocity Component in z-axis	m s^{-1}
w_w	Wind Velocity Component in z-axis	m s^{-1}
X	State vector	
x_{CG}	X Component of the Centre of Gravity	
X_P	First derivative of the state vector	
Y	Side Force	N
y_{CG}	Y Component of the Centre of Gravity	

Indices

b	Body Reference Frame
e	North East Down Coordinates
EA	Elastic Axis
HE	Horizontal Empennage
i	Elastic mode number
i	Inertia Frame
VE	Vertical Empennage
W	Wing

1 | Introduction

This chapter introduces the main background information about the science of aeroelasticity, which forms the basis of this thesis. Following this, the importance of this field will be discussed, highlighting how insufficient understanding can lead to catastrophic consequences. Subsequently, the chapter will discuss the challenges researchers face when analysing the flight dynamics model of a flexible aircraft. Afterwards, it will examine previous studies and papers that have addressed similar topics. Then, the main purpose of this work will be declared and outlined. Finally, the scope of the work will be presented, mapping out the structure of the entire thesis, and discussing any limitations within the research.

1.1 Introduction and problem statement

Aviation plays an important role in carbon dioxide (CO_2) emissions and the phenomenon of global warming. Nowadays, aviation represents 2.5% of global CO_2 emissions and contributes by 4% to global warming [1]. In response, the European Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking¹ is committed to developing and supporting new aircraft technologies that will reduce greenhouse gases by at least 30% compared to the year 2020 [4]. In this respect, the Ultra Performance Wing project (UP-Wing) has been funded by the European Union. This project aims to reduce the amount of emitted CO_2 through the development of an aircraft with an "Ultra-Performance Wing", a wing design intended to lower induced aerodynamic drag. Thereby decreasing fuel consumption and subsequently reducing CO_2 emissions. The reduction of aerodynamic drag is achieved by configuring a high aspect ratio wing, which means increasing the wingspan while reducing the mean aerodynamic chord of the wing [5]. Although a high aspect ratio wing could be a significant advantage for the aviation industry, it also presents challenges that should be taken into account. As the aspect ratio of the wing increases, the wing becomes lighter and, therefore, more flexible. This flexibility could potentially result in catastrophic consequences if it is not analysed and evaluated in sufficient depth. The question thus arises as to why the wing is flexible. In this context, it is necessary to provide an explanation of the term "aeroelasticity". The field of aeroelasticity, or the term "aeroelasticity", first appeared in the mid-thirties [6]. Before this, the aircraft was considered rigid body, which means that the structural modes or the elastic modes had a frequency that was sufficiently high in comparison to the rigid body modes. The critical stability problems occur when the frequencies of the elastic modes approach

¹The Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking is a European Union organisation that supports research and innovation programs aimed at transforming aviation to achieve sustainability and climate neutrality [2]. This organisation is a partnership between the European Commission and the European aeronautics industry [3].

those of the rigid body modes, leading to interaction, which can result in serious stability threat that vary from manageable instabilities, which can be mitigated by a pilot, to catastrophic failures. One of the earliest such catastrophic failures occurred in 1903 when the wing of the Professor Langley's monoplane collapsed. Försching [6], suggests that this may have been the first accident caused by aeroelastic circumstances, as later investigations showed that the failure was caused by static torsional divergence of the wings. In England, F.W. Lanchester carried out the first theoretical investigation in 1916 on the Handley-Page 0/400, a twin-engine bomber. This investigation was about elevator flutter, which occurs due to violent torsional vibrations in the fuselage. Lanchester suggested that the observed oscillations were caused by specific excitation mechanisms, as they could not have been excited by engine imbalance or propeller flows [6]. These incidents highlight the critical need for comprehensive aeroelastic analysis in engineering designs, particularly in aircraft design and testing. It is essential to accurately study the behaviour of a flexible aircraft under various excitation and manoeuvres before conducting real flight tests. The analysis of the aircraft dynamics in this regard is usually done by first solving the equations of motion and then evaluating their results. These equations are formulated by considering both the aerodynamic and structural models. The structural model can be analysed using a finite element analysis program, which allows for the extraction of structural properties. These properties usually include the characteristics of each elastic mode, that can be defined in terms of frequency, damping ratio, eigenvector and eigenvalues. Afterwards, the data from the finite element analysis and the aerodynamic data are integrated together and then simulated. In order to get an accurate understanding of how an aircraft reacts to certain manoeuvres, it is necessary to analyse several simulation results simultaneously, which takes time and effort. An additional challenge for the researcher is that a real-time observation of the aircraft's behaviour is not possible. In such cases, a tool is required that allows the user to animate and simulate the aircraft 'live', while the calculation of the equations of motion runs in the background and the results are visualised in real-time. In this regard, this thesis aims to develop a real-time simulation tool for flexible aircraft. This tool will integrate a self-calculated aeroelastic model, incorporating both aerodynamic and structural dynamics, with an open-source simulator. Such an integration will enable users to animate and fly customised 3-D models while displaying the real-time response of the self-calculated aeroelastic models. Hence, the tool not only enhances the understanding of aircraft behaviour, but also allows for real-time tracking. Furthermore, it offers the user the flexibility to control the aircraft either manually using a joystick or through predetermined inputs.

1.2 Literature Review

In this section, an overview of existing research in the field of flight dynamics simulation relevant to the scope of this thesis is presented and discussed. The common methodologies used by researchers to analyse and evaluate the flight dynamics model can be divided into two main approaches.

The first approach is simulation-in-the-loop (SIL), which focusses mainly on the rigid body dynamics of the unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). Usually, the algorithms or controllers to be tested are implemented in MATLAB/Simulink and then visualised using open-source flight simulators such as X-Plane, Flight Gear, or similar open-source simulators. In this regard, Bittar et al. (2014) developed a SIL method to test a guidance algorithm for UAVs, where the control and guidance algorithms run on Simulink while the aeroplane model runs on X-Plane. Communication between X-Plane and Simulink is established using the User Datagram Protocol (UDP) and utilising specific ports for this interaction, as illustrated in Fig. 1.1². Figure 1.2 shows the architecture of the SIL tool. The guidance algorithms receive navigation data from X-Plane using the UDP receiver. These algorithms then calculate reference values and send them to the control block, which processes the data and sends control surface commands through the UDP sender. X-Plane receives these commands, executes the control surface deflections, applies the relevant aerodynamic model, and generates updated navigation data. This navigation data is then transmitted back to Simulink, completing the cycle [7].

Figure 1.1: Ports used for the Network Configuration between X-Plane and Simulink [7]

Figure 1.2: Simulation in the Loop Configuration [7]

²It should be noted that the port ID number illustrated in Fig. 1.1 may vary depending on the X-Plane version being used in the project.

Such a tool is very useful as it significantly reduces costs and risks by allowing algorithms to be tested and verified before a real experimental flight test. In addition, it facilitates easy modifications to the algorithms and enables repeated testing without incurring additional costs. However, as illustrated in Fig. 1.2, the flight dynamics model employed in this tool is derived from X-Plane. This approach does not include a self-implemented plug-in that would allow users to disable the X-Plane physics engine and use a custom calculated flight model instead.

The second approach is a combination of SIL and hardware-in-the-loop (HIL), where physical components, such as microcontrollers or servomotors, are embedded in the simulation setup. Such configurations are particularly advantageous for UAVs, as they enable testing the algorithms while observing the aircraft's response in real-life and in real-time. In this regard, Ribeiro and Oliveira (2010) at the Aeronautics Institute of Technology (ITA) developed a tool for the purpose of testing a UAV autopilot controller. The configuration of the tool is represented in Fig. 1.3. As shown in the figure, the system uses Matlab/Simulink to operate the autopilot controller, X-Plane to simulate the commanded aircraft, a microcontroller to manage the flight control surfaces of the aircraft, and servos to actuate these control surfaces. These components are interconnected through data communication buses. This setup allows not only to simulate and test the autopilot controller in X-Plane, but also to transmit these commands to the microcontroller which converts these commands into servo movements, thus enabling the user to observe and track the aircraft response not only on the screen but also in the real world [8].

Figure 1.3: Hardware in the Loop Configuration [8]

However, this tool is constrained in several ways. On one hand, the configuration is not applicable to all aircraft types; for example, it is not suitable for passenger aircraft. On the other hand, similar to the tool developed by Bittar et al. (2014) [7], this tool relies on the X-Plane aircraft flight dynamics model

to compute the aircraft response, limiting the user from testing the self-implemented flight dynamics model. In addition, both tools [7] and [8] focused mainly on the rigid body models and integrated them with controllers and algorithms for testing. Hence, the flexible components of the aircraft are not considered as they were not the central scope of these tools.

On the other hand, Armijos (2022) at Technical University of Berlin aimed to develop a fast flight dynamics evaluation and simulation tool to assist researchers during the conceptual design phase of the aircraft. This tool was extended to include a real-time visualisation framework using the open-source flight simulator X-Plane. A plug-in was implemented to enable real-time communication between Simulink and X-Plane, which disables X-Plane's physics engine and allows data transfer from Simulink to X-Plane. In addition, the tool supports animating the aircraft through predetermined inputs defined in Simulink or manual input using a joystick. In a further step, this tool was used to evaluate the TU-Flex aircraft demonstrator [9]. The TU-Flex is a scaled flight demonstrator with a transport aircraft configuration and high aspect ratio (HAR) wings. It is designed to record experimental data on the interaction between the aircraft's flight dynamics and structural dynamics [10], [11]. Figure 1.4 shows the TU-Flex model flying in X-Plane.

Figure 1.4: TU-Flex Represented in X-Plane [9]

Compared to the tools developed by Bittar et al. (2014) [7] and Oliveira (2010) [8], Armijos' thesis successfully developed a tool that can perform real-time animation with a self-calculated flight dynamics model. However, this tool focusses on animating a rigid body flight dynamics model, which means that wing deformation or the interaction between the aerodynamic model and the structural model was not considered.

In contrast to the approaches mentioned above, some methodologies extend the analysis to include aerodynamic and structural models. An example of this is the master's thesis by Karkas (2003) at the University of Toronto, which offers a comprehensive approach by integrating flexible degrees of freedom into an existing rigid-body flight dynamics model. The study begins with a modal analysis using the Finite Element Analysis program ANSYS. The mode shapes and nodal displacements obtained from this modal analysis are subsequently used together with Aerodynamic Strip Theory to compute aeroelastic stability derivatives. The flexible model was specifically developed for the Rockwell B1 Bomber. This flexible model was then implemented in the UTIAS Flight Research Simulator³. The UTIAS Flight Simulator features a cockpit cab mounted on a six-degree-of-freedom (DOF) motion platform [13], as illustrated in Fig. 1.5⁴.

Figure 1.5: UTIAS Flight Research Simulator [14]

Afterwards, a dynamic analysis was performed by applying various elevator inputs to the flexible aircraft model. This "pre-flight" simulation approach is crucial to fully understand the behaviour of flexible aircraft and is particularly beneficial to pilots, enabling them to determine how to manage the flexibility of the aircraft during flights [13].

Although this work represents a significant advancement by considering the flexible dynamics of the aircraft, it also has limitations. These integrations are restricted by the availability and accessibility of a full flight simulator. In addition, such simulators are designed primarily to simulate the cockpit environment to provide pilots with an immersive experience that should be as close as possible to real-world flying conditions. Consequently, these simulators typically do not allow users to track or observe wing deformation in response to specific manoeuvres.

³The UTIAS is a Flight Research Simulator offered by the Institute for Aerospace Studies at the University of Toronto for research purposes [12].

⁴Please note that the photo of the UTIAS Simulator is sourced from a different reference than source [13], as the photo of the simulator in source [13] was not recognisable.

As previously mentioned, aeroelasticity involves an interaction between structural and aerodynamic models. This interaction requires a comprehensive modal analysis, which means examining the structural behaviour. Schulze et al. (2017) in the American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics developed two tools for identifying and animating modal shapes: the Modal Identification Software Toolbox (MIST) and MIST-IADS. These tools employ sensor output data to perform modal analysis, identifying properties such as frequency, damping ratio, and mode shapes, and presenting the results through animations and time history trends [15].

MIST is designed for post-flight analysis, meaning it cannot perform a real-time simulation. As shown in Fig. 1.6, the components of the MIST tool are structured into three main sections. The first section, indicated by the red box, displays sensor information, including time history data, location, orientation, and relative connections, which are used to identify and display the mode shape. The second section, marked by the dotted green box, visualises and animates the identified mode shapes. The third section, outlined by the dashed blue box, presents analysis results such as frequency and damping [15].

Figure 1.6: Components of the MIST Tool [15]

The second tool MIST-IADS extends the capabilities of MIST to real-time applications, making it suitable for use in engineering control rooms. The components of the MIST-IADS tool are shown in Fig. 1.7. As illustrated in Fig. 1.7a, MIST-IADS features a time history interface that displays the mode properties in real-time. Furthermore, MIST-IADS allows for real-time animation of mode shapes, as depicted in Figure 1.7b [15].

(a) Real-Time History Interface in MIST-IADS

(b) Real-Time Mode Shape Animation in MIST-IADS.

Figure 1.7: Components of the MIST-IADS Tool [15]

The effectiveness of both tool sets was demonstrated using simulated data and actual flight test data from an experimental aeroelastic UAV named mAEWing1, shown in Fig. 1.8. Figure 1.8a shows the aircraft in flight, while Fig. 1.8b indicates the chosen locations for the accelerometers [15].

(a) mAEWing1 in Real Flight

(b) Locations of the Accelerometers on mAEWing1

Figure 1.8: The UAV Model used in MATLAB-MIST and MIST-IADS [15]

These tools are essential for modal analysis, particularly in the context of ground vibration tests (GVTs). Furthermore, the tools provide beneficial information about the mode shape characteristics and animate this mode shape either in real-time or as post-processing. However, the focus of this study was solely on the structural modal analysis and the real-time animation of the mode shapes. Hence, the interaction between the structure and the aerodynamic behaviour was not of primary concern and,

therefore, the animation of such an interaction was not a significant area of investigation.

In contrast to [15], the work conducted by Su and Song (2019) at the University of Alabama presents a platform for real-time hybrid aeroelastic simulation. This platform is designed to bridge the gap between aerodynamic simulations and structural vibration experiments, thus allowing real-time data exchange between these two subsystems, as illustrated in Fig. 1.9. The platform is designed to divide the aeroelastic system into two components: An aerodynamic simulation subsystem and a structural vibration subsystem. As shown in Fig. 1.9a, the aerodynamic loads are calculated in real-time and then converted to structural loads that are applied to the physical structure. In this setup, shown in more detail in Fig. 1.9b, the aerodynamic loads derived from simulations are converted into actuator forces that drive the physical model. The response of the physical model is then measured by the sensors and sent to the aerodynamic model, which processes this data and transforms it back into aerodynamic loads, thus closing the loop. [16].

Figure 1.9: Real-Time Hybrid Aeroelastic Simulation Setup [16]

This platform offers an important advantage by simulating aeroelastic behaviour without being limited by traditional wind-tunnel testing, leading to cost reduction and allowing the testing of large-scale models. However, the platform is limited by the requirement of a physical model of the wing. Although this tool is highly useful for analysing the structural model after its development, it does not facilitate examination in the early stages of the design.

Examining the previously developed tools and platforms reveals a clear need for a tool that integrates an aeroelastic model with an open-source simulator. This tool should not only support animation, but also enable the open-source simulator to interface with self-calculated aeroelastic models. This capability would allow researchers and students to fly their aircraft models incorporating both their 3-D model designs and their self-calculated aeroelastic models. Consequently, this thesis aims to address this gap by developing a real-time flexible aircraft simulation tool. The proposed solution employs MATLAB/Simulink to simulate the aeroelastic model, incorporating both aerodynamic and structural dynamics. In addition, it uses the open-source simulator X-Plane for visualisation purposes.

1.3 Objectives

The primary objective of this thesis is to develop a visualisation framework to evaluate flexible aircraft flight dynamics models. This framework should be able to communicate with simulation tools and animate the flexible aircraft in real time. The objective is achieved by completing the following three main tasks:

1. Calculation of the Aeroelastic Model: This includes both quasi-steady and unsteady aerodynamic models.
2. Visualisation: This task is divided into creating a 3-D model in Blender and importing it into X-Plane.
3. Implementing a plug-in: This involves connecting the aeroelastic model with the visualisation tool using UDP.

In the first step, an aeroelastic model is developed using MATLAB and simulated using Simulink. This model is based on the work presented in Senger's (2023) master's thesis published at the Technical University of Berlin, entitled "Aeroelastic Derivatives Calculator for Flexible Aircraft". Senger's work involved the automation of the calculation of aeroelastic derivatives. Initially, rigid body derivatives were calculated using Athena Vortex Lattice (AVL), and the process was automated using MATLAB scripts. The tool also included an automatic extraction of eigenmodes from an already existing finite element model. Senger's work covered only quasi-steady aerodynamic calculations [17]. Later, Quesada et al. (2024) extended Senger's tool to include both quasi-steady and unsteady aerodynamics, as a subsequent modification [18]. The extended tool is the one used in this thesis. In terms of the second step, the aircraft model used in this thesis is similar to the Airbus A321neo. In this regard, an Airbus A320 model is used and extensively modified. The original wing is replaced by a custom-designed wing developed within the UP-Wing project. Comprehensive details about the aircraft are given in Ch. 3. The modifications, including rigging and animating, are performed in Blender. Afterwards, the aircraft texture is created in Armorpaint. Then, the final 3-D model is imported into X-Plane 11. More detailed information on the software tools used can be found in Ch. 3. In the final step a plug-in is implemented to establish communication between X-Plane 11 and the aeroelastic flight dynamics model. The plug-in code was implemented in C++, inspired by the architecture presented in the bachelor thesis of Armijos (2022) at Technical University of Berlin, entitled "Fast Flight Dynamics Evaluator and Simulator with Visualisation for HIL Applications" [9]. Armijos' thesis concerned the development of a rigid body derivatives calculator using MATLAB, the creation of a 3-D model in Blender, and the connection of the rigid body aerodynamic model with X-Plane using a customised plug-in [9]. While Armijos' work focused on rigid body models, this thesis extends the concept to include flexible body models, incorporating a quasi-steady and an unsteady aerodynamic model. By achieving these objectives, this thesis aims to provide a tool for real-time visualisation of flexible aircraft, enhancing a deeper understanding of aeroelastic phenomena and facilitating examination in the early stages of the design.

1.4 Scope of the work and limitations

As previously mentioned, the scope of this work involves the development of a tool to facilitate the study and evaluation of aeroelastic phenomena. However, this work has certain limitations. First, the deformation considered, both in the calculation of the aeroelastic model and in the visualisation tool, does not account for the deformation caused by the fuselage. The deformations taken into account in this study are those caused by the wing, the horizontal tailplane, and the vertical tailplane, but not those of fuselage. Additionally, the mode shapes considered in the visualisation or animation tool are limited to those consisting of bending, torsion, or a coupling of both. Thus, the translation mode shapes in the xy -plane are not animated.

In order to fulfil the objectives of this thesis, the remaining chapters are structured as follows:

- Chapter 2: The second chapter explores the theoretical background of the study. It consists of two main sections. The first section focusses on the theoretical foundation of the three different aerodynamic modelling techniques considered in this work: Rigid Body (RB), Quasi-Steady (QS), and Unsteady (US). The second section provides an overview of the software tools used in this work, such as Blender, ArmorPaint, and X-Plane.
- Chapter 3: The third chapter outlines the methodology employed to develop the animation tool. The procedures are described in detail, beginning with an explanation of the simulation tool used to calculate the flight dynamics model for the three aerodynamic modelling techniques (RB, QS, US). Then, the process of designing and animating the 3-D model in Blender is illustrated, followed by an explanation of how this model is imported into X-Plane. Afterwards, the implementation of the plug-in that enables data transfer from Simulink to X-Plane is described. The chapter concludes with a case study section presenting the technical data of the aircraft used within the developed tool.
- Chapter 4: The fourth chapter evaluates the flight dynamics model of the aircraft addressed in Chapter 3 as the case study. The evaluation begins with a stability analysis of the three aerodynamic modelling techniques (RB, QS, US). The analysis then extends to include both time-domain and frequency-domain simulations for all three aerodynamic approaches. Additionally, for the time-domain simulations, animation results generated by X-Plane are presented.
- Chapter 5: The last chapter provides a conclusion and evaluation of the entire tool, summarising the findings and the overall work.

2 | Theoretical Foundations

In this chapter, the theoretical background that is essential to understand aircraft flight dynamics is outlined. This includes the mathematical equations used for calculating and modelling the flight dynamics of flexible aircraft. First, the equations of motion for a rigid body flight mechanics model are examined. Afterwards, the equations of motion for flexible aircraft incorporating quasi-steady aerodynamics are briefly illustrated, highlighting the impact of structural flexibility. Finally, the equations of motion for flexible aircraft based on unsteady aerodynamics are summarised, integrating the influence of aerodynamic lag into the mathematical model. It should be noted that the scope of this work does not include the derivation of the equations of motion. The derivation of equations of motion for the quasi-steady approach has been thoroughly covered in the master's thesis of Senger (2023) [17], while the derivation based on the unsteady approach has been accomplished in the master's thesis of Pacala (2023) [19]. Therefore, this chapter provides a summary of the equations of motion for these aerodynamic modelling techniques. Additionally, a brief theoretical background on the integrated software applications employed in this thesis is provided.

2.1 Equations of Motion of the Rigid Body Dynamics Model

In this section, a brief derivation of the equations of motion for the rigid body is illustrated, based on the methodologies outlined in [20] and [21]. These sources provide comprehensive details on the theoretical foundations and derivation processes for rigid body dynamics.

The equations of motion can be derived by applying Newton's Second Law of Motion. This law states that the net force on an object is equal to the rate of change of the object's momentum over time. Mathematically, Newton's Second Law can be expressed as follows:

$$\left. \frac{d\vec{p}}{dt} \right|_i = \sum \vec{F} \quad (2.1)$$

where \vec{p} is the linear momentum, \vec{F} represents the forces acting on the aircraft, and $\left. \frac{d(\cdot)}{dt} \right|_i$ denotes the derivative operator with respect to time in the inertial coordinate system indexed by i .

To derive the equations of motion effectively, it is essential to choose an appropriate coordinate system to simplify the calculations. In this regard, Fig. 2.1 illustrates the reference frames considered in the analysis of aircraft flight dynamics. The inertial reference frame (IRF) (x_e, y_e, z_e) is the Local North East Down (NED) coordinate system, with x_e pointing North, y_e pointing East, and z_e pointing downward. The body frame (x_b, y_b, z_b) is a coordinate system fixed to the aircraft body, with x_b pointing towards the nose, y_b to the right, and z_b downward. For short simulations and stability analyses, the

NED frame is assumed as the IRF while neglecting the Earth's rotation. This assumption is valid because the Earth's rotation is negligible compared to the aircraft's rotation during manoeuvring. On the other hand, the body-fixed coordinate system is chosen for deriving the equations of motion because it allows the inertia tensor to be considered constant. Since variations in inertia due to changes in mass can be neglected in this frame. Figure 2.1 also illustrates the absolute aircraft velocity \vec{V}_K . Consequently, the linear momentum equation can be expressed as:

$$\vec{p} = m\vec{V}_K. \quad (2.2)$$

where \vec{p} is the linear momentum, m is the aircraft mass and \vec{V}_K refers to the absolute aircraft velocity in the Body Reference Frame (BRF). The same figure depicts the forces acting on the aircraft. Accordingly, the summation of these forces can be given as follows:

$$\sum \vec{F} = \vec{T}_b + \vec{W}_b + \vec{R}_b^A. \quad (2.3)$$

In this equation, the subscript b indicates the body-fixed coordinate system or the BRF. \vec{T}_b represents the thrust force, \vec{W}_b denotes the weight force, and \vec{R}_b^A represents the resultant aerodynamic forces, which are the combination of lift and drag forces. The superscript A stands for aerodynamic.

Figure 2.1: Aircraft Dynamic Forces and Coordinate Systems [22]

Based on Eqs. 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 and under the assumption of constant mass, the linear momentum equation describing translational acceleration in the BRF can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{u}_K \\ \dot{v}_K \\ \dot{w}_K \end{bmatrix} &= - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -r_K & q_K \\ r_K & 0 & -p_K \\ -q_K & p_K & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_K \\ v_K \\ w_K \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -g \sin \theta \\ g \cos \theta \sin \phi \\ g \cos \theta \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{m} \begin{bmatrix} T \cos \alpha_T \\ 0 \\ -T \sin \alpha_T \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ \frac{1}{m} \begin{bmatrix} -D \cos \alpha \cos \beta - Y \cos \alpha \sin \beta + L \sin \alpha \\ -D \sin \beta + Y \cos \beta \\ -D \sin \alpha \cos \beta - Y \sin \alpha \sin \beta - L \cos \alpha \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

with variables represented as: absolute velocity components (u_K, v_K, w_K), absolute angular components (p_K, q_K, r_K). D , L and T , denote the drag, lift force, and thrust, respectively. Additionally, the aerodynamic angles include the angle of attack (α) and the sideslip angle (β), while the Euler angles are represented by (ϕ, θ). Finally, the installation angle of the engine is denoted by (α_T).

For the calculation of aerodynamic angles, it is essential to first define the relative velocity of the aircraft with respect to the air, denoted as \vec{V} . When observing the aircraft from an Earth-based reference frame, the relative velocity can be defined as:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{bmatrix}}_{\vec{V}} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} u_k \\ v_k \\ w_k \end{bmatrix}}_{\vec{V}_k} - \mathbf{T}_{be} \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} u_w \\ v_w \\ w_w \end{bmatrix}}_{\vec{V}_w} \quad (2.5)$$

where

$$\mathbf{T}_{be} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi \cos \theta & \cos \psi \sin \phi \sin \theta - \cos \phi \sin \psi & \cos \phi \cos \psi \sin \theta + \sin \phi \sin \psi & -\sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \sin \psi & \cos \phi \cos \psi + \sin \phi \sin \psi \sin \theta & \cos \phi \sin \psi \sin \theta - \cos \psi \sin \phi & \cos \theta \cos \phi \\ \sin \phi \sin \theta & \sin \phi \cos \psi \cos \theta - \cos \phi \sin \psi & \sin \phi \sin \psi \cos \theta + \cos \phi \cos \psi & \cos \theta \sin \phi \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2.6)$$

Here, the wind velocity V_w is defined in the NED coordinate system and subsequently transformed into the BRF using the transformation matrix T_{be} as presented in Eq. 2.6. In this equation the variables ϕ, θ and ψ represent bank angle, pitch angle, and heading angle, respectively. These angles are known as Euler angles. Consequently, the relative velocity can also be formulated as:

$$V = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2 + w^2} \quad (2.7)$$

Figure 2.2 depicts the aerodynamic angles α and β . These angles are defined as the angles between the aerodynamic frame (x_a, y_a, z_a) and the BRF. Applying trigonometric principles, the aerodynamic angles can finally be determined as follows:

$$\alpha = \arctan \frac{w}{u} \quad (2.8)$$

$$\beta = \arcsin \frac{v}{V} \quad (2.9)$$

Figure 2.2: Aerodynamic Forces and Angles in Aerodynamic and Body-Fixed Coordinate System [22]

The forces acting on the aircraft result in changes in the angular momentum, which is equivalent to the sum of the moments. The angular momentum equation can be expressed as follows:

$$\left. \frac{d\vec{h}}{dt} \right|_i = \sum \vec{M} \quad (2.10)$$

with \vec{h} equivalent to:

$$\vec{h} = J \times \vec{\omega}_K \quad (2.11)$$

where J is the inertia tensor and $\vec{\omega}_K$ represents the absolute angular velocity of the aircraft, which corresponds to $[p_k, q_k, r_k]$. It should be noted that for conventional aircraft, it is often assumed that the aircraft is symmetric in the $x_b z_b$ -plane. This assumption eliminates the terms J_{xy} and J_{yz} from the J matrix. The right hand side of Eq. 2.10 is the summation of moments around the centre of gravity (CG) and can be defined as:

$$\sum \vec{M}_{CG} = \vec{M}_{CG}^A + \vec{M}_{CG}^T \quad (2.12)$$

where \vec{M}_{CG}^A represents the moment resulting from aerodynamic forces, and \vec{M}_{CG}^T describes the moment resulting from thrust forces.

From Eqs. 2.10, 2.11 and 2.12, and considering the transformation from the inertia body frame to the BRF with a constant inertia tensor J , the rotational acceleration in the BRF can be obtained as follows:

$$\dot{p}_K = \frac{J_{xz}(J_{xx} - J_{yy} + J_{zz})p_K q_K - [J_{zz}(J_{zz} - J_{yy}) + J_{xz}^2]q_K r_K + J_{zz}J_{zz}L^{tot} + J_{xz}N^{tot}}{J_{xx}J_{zz} - J_{xz}^2} \quad (2.13)$$

$$\dot{q}_K = \frac{(J_{zz} - J_{xx})p_K r_K - J_{xz}(p_K^2 - r_K^2) + M^{tot}}{J_{yy}} \quad (2.14)$$

$$\dot{r}_K = \frac{[J_{xx}(J_{xx} - J_{yy}) + J_{xz}^2]p_K q_K - J_{xz}(J_{zz} - J_{yy})q_K r_K + J_{xz}L^{tot} + J_{xx}N^{tot}}{J_{xx}J_{zz} - J_{xz}^2} \quad (2.15)$$

where L^{tot} , M^{tot} and N^{tot} representing the aerodynamic and propulsive moments.

The angular velocity components p_k , q_k , r_k in the BRF can be used to define Euler angles. Since the derivatives of Euler angles are functions of the angular velocity components, as illustrated in the following equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{\psi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \sin \phi \tan \theta & \cos \phi \tan \theta \\ 0 & \cos \phi & -\sin \phi \\ 0 & \sin \phi / \cos \theta & \cos \phi / \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p_K \\ q_K \\ r_K \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.16)$$

To complete the equation of motion, a set of equations is required to describe the position of the aircraft. These equations describe the position vector from the inertial point to the CG of the aircraft. Consequently, these equations can be derived by transforming the absolute velocity back to the inertia frame, as defined in the following equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_{CG} \\ \dot{y}_{CG} \\ -\dot{H} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T}_{eb} \mathbf{V}_{Kb} = \mathbf{T}_{eb} \begin{bmatrix} u_K \\ v_K \\ w_K \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.17)$$

with $T_{eb} = T_{be}^T$.

Finally, from equations 2.7, 2.8 and 2.9 the values of \dot{V} , $\dot{\alpha}$ and $\dot{\beta}$ can be obtained and together with Eqs. 2.13, 2.14, 2.15, 2.16 and 2.17 the set of equations of motion are completed. For numerical solutions, the set of equations of motion can be summarized as follows:

$$\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \dot{V} \\ \dot{\beta} \\ \dot{\alpha} \\ \dot{p}_k \\ \dot{q}_k \\ \dot{r}_k \\ \dot{\Phi} \\ \dot{\Theta} \\ \dot{\Psi} \\ \dot{X}_{CG} \\ \dot{Y}_{CG} \\ \dot{H} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{x}} = \mathcal{F}_{\text{nonlinear}} \left[\underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} V \\ \beta \\ \alpha \\ p_k \\ q_k \\ r_k \\ \Phi \\ \Theta \\ \Psi \\ X_{CG} \\ Y_{CG} \\ H \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{x}}, \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \delta_a \\ \delta_r \\ \delta_e \\ \delta_t \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{U}}, \text{Wind} \right] \quad (2.18)$$

It is important to note that this set of equations of motion can be formulated to include the kinematic accelerations in the BRF. Equation 2.18 can be defined as a function of time, as follows:

$$\dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathcal{F}_{\text{nonlinear}}(\mathbf{X}(t), \mathbf{U}(t)) \quad (2.19)$$

where $\mathcal{F}_{\text{nonlinear}}$ represents the nonlinear equations of motion, X denotes the state vector, and U is the control vector. In a subsequent step, these equations are solved using numerical integration algorithms, given a specified initial condition and time step. This process is performed to obtain a trimmed aircraft model for a given flight condition. Following this, the flight dynamics model is linearised around the trim points to derive the state-space representation of the model, which is defined as follows:

$$\dot{\underline{x}} = \underline{A}\underline{x} + \underline{B}\underline{u} \quad (2.20)$$

$$\underline{y} = \underline{C}\underline{x} + \underline{D}\underline{u} \quad (2.21)$$

where \underline{A} is the dynamic matrix, \underline{B} the control matrix, \underline{C} the output matrix and \underline{D} the feedthrough matrix. The vectors \underline{x} , \underline{u} and \underline{y} , are the state vector, the control vector and the output vector, respectively. The state-space representation captures the linearised dynamics derived from the nonlinear behaviour of the system. This linearised model represents the dynamics near the trimmed conditions, which corresponds to a physical equilibrium point of the system. The linearisation process is crucial for enabling the application of linear control design techniques and for assessing local stability and margins. Consequently, this approach aids in a deeper understanding of the non-linear behaviour of the system.

2.2 Equations of Motion of the Quasi-Steady Flexible Dynamics Model

In this section, the rigid body equations of motion are adapted to integrate the structural dynamic model with the aerodynamic model using a quasi-steady modelling approach. This method assumes that the incremental aerodynamic loads at any given time depend only on the airfoil's displacement and torsion at that moment. This implies that there is no time delay between the airfoil movement and the resulting aerodynamic loads. Following this approach, this section provides a summary of the equations of motion as outlined by Silvestre (2008) in [23]. A detailed derivation of the equations of motion can be found in [24].

To derive the equations of motion for a flexible dynamics model, the Lagrange equations are used. These equations describe the motion of a system based on its kinetic energy T , potential energy U , structural damping Γ and generalised loads Q_k . Before deriving the kinetic energy, it is essential to first explain Fig. 2.3. This figure illustrates a flexible aircraft in flight and highlights the global body reference frame (GBRF) relative to the IRF. Additionally, Fig. 2.3 shows a mass element dm , which is positioned by the vector p . This vector represents the position of the mass element relative to the CG of the aircraft. The vector R describes the position of the same mass element relative to the origin of the IRF O_I . For the undeformed aircraft, the mass element is located by the vector p_r relative to the CG of the aircraft. Lastly, the vector R_0 specifies the position of the aircraft's CG in relation to the origin of the IRF O_I .

Figure 2.3: Flexible Aircraft and the Global Body and Inertia Reference Frames [25]

According to the convention illustrated in Fig. 2.3, and under the assumptions that the aircraft's structural density ρ remains constant during deformation and that the inertia tensor J is invariable, the kinetic energy T of the aircraft can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} T &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V \frac{d\vec{R}}{dt} \cdot \frac{d\vec{R}}{dt} \rho dV \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V \left(\frac{d\vec{R}_0}{dt} + \frac{d\vec{p}}{dt} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{d\vec{R}_0}{dt} + \frac{d\vec{p}}{dt} \right) \rho dV \\ &= \frac{1}{2} m \frac{d\vec{R}_0}{dt} \cdot \frac{d\vec{R}_0}{dt} + \frac{1}{2} \omega^T \mathbf{J} \omega + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_{ii} (\dot{\eta}_i)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

where V represents the aircraft velocity, m the mass of the aircraft, ω the angular velocity relative to the IRF, μ_{ii} the generalised mass matrix, and η_i the modal amplitude. In Eq. 2.22, the index i refers to the number of modes. The operator $\frac{d(\cdot)}{dt}$ represents the time derivative with respect to BRF. It should be pointed out that the vector p can be decomposed into its rigid and elastic components, p_r and p_d respectively.

The potential energy U of a flexible aircraft is defined as the sum of gravitational energy and deformation energy, and it is defined as follows:

$$U = mg(x_{CG} \sin \theta - y_{CG} \cos \theta \sin \phi - z_{CG} \cos \theta \cos \phi) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_{ii} (\omega_{n,i})^2 (\eta_i)^2 \quad (2.23)$$

where $\omega_{n,i}$ is the natural frequency of the i -th mode.

Considering the structural damping forces of the aircraft as an equivalent viscous damping force, the Rayleigh function can be used to define the energy associated with the viscous damping force [26]. Consequently, the structural dissipation can be determined as follows:

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_{ii} (2\xi_i \omega_{n,i}) (\dot{\eta}_i)^2 \quad (2.24)$$

where the variable ξ_i represents the generalised modal damping for the i -th mode.

The generalised loads can be defined in the generalised coordinates as follows:

$$Q_k = \int_V \vec{f} \cdot \frac{\partial \vec{R}}{\partial q_k} \quad (2.25)$$

where $\vec{f} = f_x \vec{x}_B + f_y \vec{y}_B + f_z \vec{z}_B$, represent the distributed load per unit volume of the aircraft, and q_k is the generalised coordinate for k number of modes.

By considering Eq. 2.22, 2.23, 2.24 and 2.25, the Lagrange equations can be applied as follows:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{q}_k} \right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial q_k} + \frac{\partial D}{\partial \dot{q}_k} = Q_k \quad (2.26)$$

where $L = T - U$ represents the Lagrange Matrix, and D describes the structural damping. Equations 2.25 and 2.26 together yield the set of equations of motion as shown below:

$$\dot{u} = \frac{X}{m} + rv - qw - g \sin \theta \quad (2.27)$$

$$\dot{v} = \frac{Y}{m} - ru + pw + g \cos \theta \sin \phi \quad (2.28)$$

$$\dot{w} = \frac{Z}{m} + qu - pv + g \cos \theta \cos \phi \quad (2.29)$$

$$I_{xx}\dot{p} - I_{xy}\dot{q} - I_{xz}\dot{r} - I_{yz}(q^2 - r^2) - (I_{yy} - I_{zz})qr - p(I_{xz}q - I_{xy}r) = L \quad (2.30)$$

$$-I_{xy}\dot{p} + I_{yy}\dot{q} - I_{yz}\dot{r} - I_{xz}(r^2 - p^2) - (I_{zz} - I_{xx})pr - q(I_{xy}r - I_{yz}p) = M \quad (2.31)$$

$$-I_{xz}\dot{p} - I_{yz}\dot{q} + I_{zz}\dot{r} - I_{xy}(p^2 - q^2) - (I_{xx} - I_{yy})pq - r(I_{yz}p - I_{xz}q) = N \quad (2.32)$$

$$\ddot{\eta}_i + 2\xi_i\omega_{n,i}\dot{\eta}_i + \omega_{n,i}^2\eta_i = \frac{Q_{\eta_i|W,HE} + Q_{\eta_i|VE}}{\mu_{ii}} \quad \text{for } i = 1 : n \quad (2.33)$$

Equations 2.27, 2.28 and 2.29 describe the translational motion, while Eqs. 2.30, 2.31 and 2.32 define the rotational motion. Finally, Eq. 2.33 determines the structural dynamics with n DOF. The terms $Q_{\eta_i|W,HE}$ and $Q_{\eta_i|VE}$ in Eq. 2.33 refer to the generalised loads generated by the wing, horizontal empennage (HE), and vertical empennage (VE) as a result of the modal amplitude η_i , where i represents the amount of modes. The forces (X , Y , Z) and moments (L , M , N) are derived and calculated as functions of the aerodynamic coefficients. The formulation of the aerodynamic coefficients for the flexible aircraft can be found in [23].

2.3 Equations of Motion of the Unsteady Flexible Dynamics Model

Unsteady aerodynamics involves studying the aerodynamic forces on a moving body, where these forces vary over time due to changes in flow conditions or the motion of the body itself. This phenomenon is important for analysing flexible aircraft wings, rotor blades, and control surfaces, where airfoil movements are not instantaneous but have a time delay in response to aerodynamic loads. Unsteady aerodynamic forces can be divided into circulatory and non-circulatory parts. As shown in Fig. 2.4, the circulatory component arises from the bound vortices around the airfoil, as described by Theodorsen's function. The flow curls around the trailing edge from the lower surface to the upper surface at high speed, generating vortices. These vortices are influenced by the history of the airfoil's motion and the flow conditions. Consequently, this results in a time-delayed effect on the aerodynamic forces, as the airfoil's wake and the shedding of vortices impact the current aerodynamic behaviour of the

airfoil. Such an interaction captures the lag between the airfoil's motion and the resulting aerodynamic forces. The non-circulatory component, often referred to as the added mass effect, is associated with the acceleration of the air mass around the body and reflects instantaneous changes in pressure distribution as the airfoil accelerates [27], [28], [29]. Understanding these components is crucial for accurately predicting the dynamic response and stability of aeroelastic systems under unsteady flow conditions. In this section a summary of the equations of motion according to Silvestre (2012) is provided [25], with a comprehensive derivation available in the same source.

Figure 2.4: Circulated Flow around an Airfoil [29]

Analogous to the quasi-steady approach, the Lagrange Equations are also employed here to derive the set of equations, which are summarised in Equations 2.34, 2.35, 2.36 and 2.37. Equations 2.34 and 2.35 are derived from the linear momentum and angular momentum equations, respectively. Equation 2.36 describes the structural dynamics, while Equation 2.37 represents the aerodynamic lag states.

$$\dot{\mathbf{V}}|_{B(G)}(t) = -\boldsymbol{\omega}|_{B(G)}(t) \times \mathbf{V}|_{B(G)}(t) + \mathbf{T}_{B(G)I}(t)\mathbf{G}|_I + \frac{1}{m}\mathbf{F}^{\text{ext}}|_{B(G)}(t) \quad (2.34)$$

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}|_{B(G)}(t) = -\mathbf{J}^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\omega}|_{B(G)}(t) \times (\mathbf{J}\boldsymbol{\omega}|_{B(G)}(t))) + \mathbf{J}^{-1}\mathbf{M}^{\text{ext}}|_{B(G)}(t) \quad (2.35)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}(t) \\ \ddot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}(t) \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_e \times n_e} & \mathbf{I}_{n_e \times n_e} \\ \boldsymbol{\Pi}_1(t) & \boldsymbol{\Pi}_2(t) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\eta}(t) \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}(t) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_e \times n_e} \\ \boldsymbol{\Pi}_3(t) \end{bmatrix} (\boldsymbol{\lambda}_1(t) + \boldsymbol{\lambda}_2(t)) \\ &+ \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_e \times n_e} \\ \boldsymbol{\Pi}_4(t) \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_{\text{state}}(t) + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_e \times n_e} \\ \boldsymbol{\Pi}_5(t) \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{\text{control}}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.36)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_1(t) &= 2V(t)a_1\mathbf{c}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\lambda}_1(t) + A_1\dot{\mathbf{w}}_{3/4}^f(t) \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\lambda}}_2(t) &= 2V(t)a_2\mathbf{c}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\lambda}_2(t) + A_2\dot{\mathbf{w}}_{3/4}^f(t). \end{aligned} \quad (2.37)$$

Considering Eqs. 2.34 and 2.35, the variables denoted by $(\cdot)|_{B(G)}$ refer to the GBRF, where $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ is the angular velocity and V is the linear velocity. Both V and $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ are relative to the IRF but expressed in the GBRF. The term $\mathbf{T}_{B(G)I}$ represents the transformation matrix from the IRF to the GBRF. The gravity acceleration vector $\mathbf{G}|_I$ is equivalent to $[0, 0, g]^T$. Additionally, m denotes the aircraft mass, \mathbf{J} is the inertia tensor matrix, and $\mathbf{F}^{\text{ext}}|_{B(G)}$ and $\mathbf{M}^{\text{ext}}|_{B(G)}$ are the external forces and moments acting on the aircraft, including propulsive and aerodynamic forces and moments. The terms $\mathbf{F}^{\text{ext}}|_{B(G)}$ and

$\mathbf{M}^{\text{ext}}|_{B(G)}$ are calculated and formulated differently compared to the quasi-steady approach, as in the unsteady model, forces and moments consist of contributions from both circulated and non-circulated flow. These terms can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{F}_A|_{B(G)}(t) &= \mathbf{F}_A^{(NC)}|_{B(G)}(t) + \mathbf{F}_A^{(C)}|_{B(G)}(t) \\ &= \rho(t)\mathbf{F}_{A\ddot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\ddot{\eta}(t) \\ &\quad + \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{F}_{A\dot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\dot{\eta}(t) + \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{F}_{A\dot{\eta}}^{(C)}(t)\dot{\eta}(t) \\ &\quad + \rho(t)V^2(t)\mathbf{F}_{A\eta}^{(C)}(t)\eta(t) \\ &\quad + \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{F}_{A\lambda}^{(C)}(t)(\lambda_1(t) + \lambda_2(t))\end{aligned}\quad (2.38)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{M}_A|_{B(G)}(t) &= \mathbf{M}_A^{(NC)}|_{B(G)}(t) + \mathbf{M}_A^{(C)}|_{B(G)}(t) \\ &= \rho(t)\mathbf{M}_{A\ddot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\ddot{\eta}(t) \\ &\quad + \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{M}_{A\dot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\dot{\eta}(t) + \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{M}_{A\dot{\eta}}^{(C)}(t)\dot{\eta}(t) \\ &\quad + \rho(t)V^2(t)\mathbf{M}_{A\eta}^{(NC)}(t)\eta(t) + \rho(t)V^2(t)\mathbf{M}_{A\eta}^{(C)}(t)\eta(t) \\ &\quad + \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{M}_{A\lambda}^{(C)}(t)(\lambda_1(t) + \lambda_2(t)).\end{aligned}\quad (2.39)$$

In Eqs. 2.38 and 2.39, η represents the modal amplitude vector, while λ_1 and λ_2 denote the first and second lag state vectors per strip, respectively. The derivation and formulation of the coefficients in these equations are explained comprehensively in [25].

For Eq.2.36, the matrices $\mathbf{\Pi}_1$, $\mathbf{\Pi}_2$, $\mathbf{\Pi}_3$ and $\mathbf{\Pi}_4$ are defined as shown in Eq. 2.40. The generalised loads \mathbf{Q}_η for the k -th elastic mode are expressed as in Eq. 2.41.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{\Pi}_1(t) &= \left[\boldsymbol{\mu} - \rho(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\ddot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\right]^{-1} \left[-\boldsymbol{\mu}\omega_n^2 + \rho(t)V^2(t)\left(\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\eta}^{(NC)}(t) + \mathbf{Q}_{\eta\eta}^{(C)}(t)\right)\right] \\ \mathbf{\Pi}_2(t) &= \left[\boldsymbol{\mu} - \rho(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\dot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\right]^{-1} \left[-2\boldsymbol{\mu}\xi\omega_n + \rho(t)V(t)\left(\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\dot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t) + \mathbf{Q}_{\eta\dot{\eta}}^{(C)}(t)\right)\right] \\ \mathbf{\Pi}_3(t) &= \left[\boldsymbol{\mu} - \rho(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\ddot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\right]^{-1} \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\lambda}(t) \\ \mathbf{\Pi}_4(t) &= \left[\boldsymbol{\mu} - \rho(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\ddot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\right]^{-1} \frac{1}{2}\rho(t)V^2(t)S\bar{c}\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\mathbf{x}_{state}}^{(QS)}(t) \\ \mathbf{\Pi}_5(t) &= \left[\boldsymbol{\mu} - \rho(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\ddot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\right]^{-1} \frac{1}{2}\rho(t)V^2(t)S\bar{c}\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\mathbf{u}_{control}}^{(QS)}(t)\end{aligned}\quad (2.40)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{Q}_{\eta_k}(t) &= \mathbf{Q}_{\eta_k}^{(NC)}(t) + \mathbf{Q}_{\eta_k}^{(C)}(t) \\ &= \rho(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta_k\ddot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\ddot{\eta}(t) \\ &\quad + \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta_k\dot{\eta}}^{(NC)}(t)\dot{\eta}(t) + \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta_k\dot{\eta}}^{(C)}(t)\dot{\eta}(t) \\ &\quad + \rho(t)V^2(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta_k\eta}^{(NC)}(t)\eta(t) + \rho(t)V^2(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta_k\eta}^{(C)}(t)\eta(t) \\ &\quad + \rho(t)V(t)\mathbf{Q}_{\eta_k\lambda}^{(C)}(t)(\lambda_1(t) + \lambda_2(t)).\end{aligned}\quad (2.41)$$

The terms $\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\mathbf{x}_{state}}^{(QS)}$ and $\mathbf{Q}_{\eta\mathbf{u}_{control}}^{(QS)}$ represent the contributions of the aircraft state and control surface deflections to the generalised elastic loads, respectively. In this thesis, these terms are computed using

the quasi-steady aerodynamics modelling approach and strip theory. Detailed calculations of these terms can be found in [23]. It should be noted that the state vector \mathbf{X}_{state} includes the aircraft's angle of attack α , the side slip angle β and the normalised angular rates $\bar{p}, \bar{q}, \bar{r}$. The angular rates are normalised by the factor $V/(\bar{c}/2)$, making them dimensionless. On the other hand, the control vector $\mathbf{u}_{control}$ includes the deflections of the ailerons, elevator, flaps, and rudder.

The formulation of the term \mathbf{Q}_{η_k} in this project deviates from the approach presented by Silvestre (2012) [25]. In Silvestre's work, \mathbf{Q}_{η_k} is defined as a diagonal matrix, effectively decoupling the elastic modes. In contrast, this project defines \mathbf{Q}_{η_k} as a full-square matrix, with the number of rows and columns equal to the number of elastic modes. This formulation accounts for the coupling between the elastic modes.

Finally, considering Eq. 2.37, the term $w_{3/4}^f(t)$ represents the spanwise acceleration at the three-quarter chord point. This term can be determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} w_{3/4}^f(y_j, t) &= \varphi^{EA}(y_j)\dot{\eta}(t) - V(t)\gamma^{EA}(y_j)\boldsymbol{\eta}(t) + (x_{3/4_j} - x_{EA_j})\gamma^{EA}(y_j)\dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}(t) \\ &= [\varphi^{EA}(y_j) + (x_{3/4_j} - x_{EA_j})\gamma^{EA}(y_j)]\dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}}(t) - V(t)\gamma^{EA}(y_j)\boldsymbol{\eta}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.42)$$

where φ^{EA} and γ^{EA} represent the bending and torsion of the structure at the elastic axis EA , respectively.

2.4 Summarised Theoretical Comparison

This section provides a brief summary of the differences between the three aerodynamic modelling approaches considered in this work: Rigid body, quasi-steady and unsteady. As shown in Table 2.1, at first instance the primary differences lie in the equations of motion and the state vectors of the system. For rigid body dynamics, the flight dynamics equations include the linear and angular momentum equations. The three translational equations of motion are derived from the linear momentum equation, while the three rotational equations of motion are defined by the angular momentum equation. In the case of flexible aircraft with high aspect ratio, the structural dynamic equations must also be considered. Two aerodynamic modelling approaches are applicable here: the quasi-steady approach and the unsteady approach. In the quasi-steady approach, it is assumed that there is no time delay between the airfoil movement and the generated aerodynamic load. Consequently, only the flight dynamics and structural dynamics are considered. The system's state vector is extended to include the amplitude of the elastic modes η and the rate of change of this amplitude $\dot{\eta}$ with respect to time. In contrast, the unsteady approach takes into account not only the structural dynamics but also the time delay between the airfoil movement and the generated load. Therefore, the equations of motion for the unsteady approach also include the aerodynamic lag state equations. Consequently, the state vector of the unsteady approach is further extended to include the first and second lag states λ_1 and λ_2 . It should be noted that the flight dynamics equations for all three approaches are functions of the external forces and moments acting on the aircraft. The modelling of these forces and moments differs among the approaches. In this work, the calculation of rigid body forces and moments is based on

rigid body coefficients extracted from AVL. For the quasi-steady approach, forces and moments are calculated using the formulation of the flexible aerodynamic coefficients, as described in [23]. For the unsteady approach, the forces and moments are calculated using the unsteady flexible aerodynamic coefficients formulated in [25].

Table 2.1: Summarised Comparison of Aerodynamic Approaches

	Rigid Body	Quasi-Steady	Unsteady
EOM	Flight Dynamics Equations	Flight Dynamics Equations Structural Dynamics Equations	Flight Dynamics Equations Structural Dynamics Equations Aerodynamic Lag States Equations
States	$V, \alpha, \beta, p_k, q_k, r_k, \phi, \theta, \psi,$ X_{CG}, Y_{CG} and H	$V, \alpha, \beta, p_k, q_k, r_k, \phi, \theta, \psi,$ $X_{CG}, Y_{CG}, H, \eta_i$ and $\dot{\eta}_i$	$V, \alpha, \beta, p_k, q_k, r_k, \phi, \theta, \psi,$ $X_{CG}, Y_{CG}, H, \eta_i, \dot{\eta}_i, \lambda_1$ and λ_2

2.5 Integrated Software Applications

This section provides a brief theoretical background to each programme used in this thesis to develop and visualise the flexible aircraft simulation. This overview covers the software used at different stages of the project.

2.5.1 Athena Vortex Lattice (AVL)

AVL is a computational program developed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) for the aerodynamic and flight dynamic analysis of rigid aircraft configurations. The program is based on the Vortex Lattice Method (VLM), which models aircraft surfaces as a series of bound vortices to calculate aerodynamic forces and moments. AVL is capable of performing trim calculations, dynamic stability analysis, and other aerodynamic evaluations. Dynamic stability analysis involves the calculation of aerodynamic forces and moments and their corresponding coefficients. Furthermore, aerodynamic calculations include the determination of parameters such as the Oswald factor, the angle of attack, or the induced drag coefficient. In addition, the software can handle general non-linear flight states and provides a comprehensive linearisation of the aerodynamic model around a given flight state, considering the mass properties of the aircraft [30], [31], [32]. Since the aerodynamic coefficients of a flexible flight dynamics model consist of both rigid body and flexible components, the AVL software is used in this project to compute the aerodynamic coefficients of the rigid body model.

2.5.2 Blender/ArmorPaint

Blender is an open-source software widely used in the fields of 3-D modelling and animation. It encloses the entire 3-D content creation pipeline, including modelling, rigging, animating, rendering, texturing, video editing, and game creation [33]. Blender's extensive features, particularly for rigging and animation, make it an ideal choice for this thesis. In Blender, users can precisely control how the rigging elements depend on each other, allowing the inheritance of movement from one rigging element to

another, resulting in smooth and realistic animations. These robust rigging and animation capabilities are crucial for animating the lifting surfaces of the aircraft in this work, ensuring realistic movement. Additionally, Blender supports the installation of additional add-ons, allowing enhanced functionality and integration with other tools. Specifically, for this research project, the add-on "xplane2blender" was used to enable communication and data extraction between Blender and the flight simulator X-Plane. However, this add-on could not extract textures from Blender that X-Plane could recognise. Therefore, an external programme called ArmorPaint was used to generate a 2-D image from a 3-D surface.

ArmorPaint is an open-source 3-D painting software designed for creating physically-based rendering (PBR) textures [34]. It allows users to paint directly on 3-D models, creating detailed and realistic textures for use in games, films, and other digital media. ArmorPaint supports various file formats, facilitating integration with other 3-D modelling tools. Consequently, ArmorPaint is suitable for this work, as Blender files could be easily imported into it for painting. Additionally, the images produced by ArmorPaint are compatible with X-Plane.

2.5.3 Open Vehicle Sketch Pad (OpenVSP)

OpenVSP is an open-source parametric aircraft geometry tool originally developed by NASA. This tool is primarily used for creating 3-D models during the conceptual design process. In addition, it allows users to perform various types of aerodynamic analysis, structural analysis, mass properties analysis, and projected area analysis. These analyses utilise vortex lattice or panel methods through the VSPAERO tool. Furthermore, OpenVSP includes integrated tools for mesh generation, supporting both computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and finite element analysis (FEA) [35]. A notable feature of OpenVSP is its compatibility with other software, enabling the import and export of multiple geometry formats. Such flexibility enhances its integration with other 3-D modelling programs, which is particularly important for this thesis. After modelling the aircraft wing in OpenVSP, the model can be exported in the ".obj" format, which is compatible with Blender. Subsequently, the wing model can be further modified and animated in Blender.

2.5.4 X-Plane/Planemaker

X-Plane, developed by Laminar Research, is a flight simulator used for various applications, including pilot training, engineering design, and aviation research. Unlike most flight simulators that rely on flight dynamics models based on stability derivatives, X-Plane's simulator operates by analysing the geometric shape of any aircraft to predict its flight characteristics. This involves breaking the aircraft into small elements and calculating the forces on each element. These forces are then converted into accelerations based on the aircraft's mass and centre of gravity, which are mathematically integrated to determine velocities and positions. X-Plane's methodology ensures a reliable simulation system, which is certified by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) for pilot training. A notable feature of X-Plane is its high-resolution graphic environment, covering the Earth from 74 degrees north to

60 degrees south latitude and including over 35,000 airports. In addition, one of the most important features of X-Plane is its ability to allow users to fly their own customised aircraft using the integrated software PlaneMaker. This tool enables users to model customised aeroplanes or helicopters. Furthermore, X-Plane supports information exchange with external environments through a UDP connection [36]. The requirement for a flight simulator with a high-resolution graphic environment and the ability to communicate with external environments, specifically Simulink, make X-Plane an ideal choice for this project. In addition, X-Plane also allows communication with Blender through the add-on "xplane2blender", as described in Section 2.5.2.

2.5.5 User Datagram Protocol (UDP)

The UDP is a connectionless communication protocol which is mainly used to establish fast connections. Connectionless protocols do not establish permanent connections between sender and receiver, and consequently send the data packets independently of each other. UDP was introduced as an alternative to the predominantly used Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) for applications that require low latency. In a UDP transmission, the data is sent and received as fixed blocks. The speed advantages result primarily from the fact that certain checking functions are omitted in UDP transmissions. As a result, the overhead of the transmitted data packets is reduced. On the other hand, this also increases the risk of data loss. The header of a UDP data packet contains up to four fields. Analogue to TCP, the port number of the sender and the port of the recipient are each stored in a separate field. Port numbers for UDP are allocated between 0 and 65535. Furthermore, the length of the packet is specified to verify the packet's completeness. Additionally, the so-called checksum is stored as an optional field in the header, to determine errors in the transmission. Each of these fields is 16 bits in size, so the total size of the header can be up to 8 bytes [37]. The TCP header size, on the other hand, is between 20 and 60 bytes [38]. Typical applications of the User Datagram Protocol are audio and video transmissions or online games where a high transmission rate is required [37]. Since this work requires real-time data transfer, UDP is used due to its low-latency transmission capabilities. Additionally, UDP facilitates seamless communication with X-Plane, enabling real-time flight simulation data transfer from Simulink to X-Plane.

3 | Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodology employed to develop an animation tool that facilitates communication between Simulink and X-Plane, enabling real-time animation of flexible aircraft in X-Plane. Each phase, from initial model creation to practical implementation, is described in separate sections. An overview of the systematic approach taken in this work is illustrated in Fig. 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Workflow of the Real-Time Flexible Aircraft Simulator

As shown in Figure 3.1, the procedures for the aeroelastic simulator primarily consist of two major components: the calculation of the aeroelastic flight dynamics model and the visualisation process. The calculation of the aeroelastic flight dynamics model involves three critical steps. First, the rigid body stability derivatives are computed using AVL. In a next step, a modal analysis is performed utilising the finite element analysis software NASTRAN to extract structural properties, such as eigenvalues and eigenvectors. Afterwards, these parameters are integrated to calculate the aeroelastic flight dynamics model in MATLAB and simulate it in Simulink. For the visualisation part, a 3-D model is created, rigged, and animated in Blender. This model is then textured using Armorpaint. Then, the textured 3-D model is imported into PlaneMaker and saved as an ".acf" file. This format is required to import the 3-D model into X-Plane. Once these steps are completed, the graphical design model is ready for use. Finally, Simulink transmits the calculated data to X-Plane via a C++ plug-in using UDP.

3.1 Aeroelastic Flight Dynamics Model Calculations

The calculation of the aeroelastic flight dynamics model is a crucial part of the methodology and involves several steps to accurately simulate the interaction between aerodynamic forces and structural dynamics. Analogous to Ch. 2, the explanation begins with the rigid body simulator structure. It then builds upon this foundation to include an aeroelastic flight dynamics model based on quasi-steady and unsteady aerodynamics modelling techniques.

3.1.1 Rigid Body Flight Dynamics Model Calculation

Figure 3.2 describes the rigid body simulator flow chart. As a first step, the aircraft parameters are defined in the script "<Aircraft Name>_Parameters.m". These parameters include four categories:

- Geometric parameters, for example, the wing span, the HE span, the VE span, and the aerodynamic chord, among other geometric parameters.
- Inertia properties, such as aircraft mass, centre of gravity, and inertial moments.
- Reference flight conditions, like Mach number and altitude.
- Propulsive properties, including engine positions and maximum thrust.

This file is initialised in the "main.m" script to start the calculation of the flight dynamics model and to trim the aircraft for the given condition. The equations of motion of the rigid body model, explained in Sec. 2.1 (see Eq. 2.18), are implemented in a script named "dynamics.m". Since the equations of motion are functions of the aerodynamic and propulsive forces and moments, two subfunctions are implemented: "aerodynamics.m" and "propulsion.m". The "aerodynamics.m" function is responsible for calculating the aerodynamic forces and moments, while the calculation of propulsive forces and moments are carried out in "propulsion.m".

Figure 3.2: Simplified Flow Chart of the Rigid Body Simulator

The "aerodynamics.m" function requires two kinds of inputs: the parameters defined in "<Aircraft Name>_Parameters.m" and the rigid body stability derivatives. These rigid body stability derivatives are obtained using the AVL software. In AVL, the wing, the horizontal tail and the vertical tail of the aircraft used in this project (F25/UPWing)⁵ are modelled with the geometric parameters and profile data given for each wing. By providing the programme with parameters such as Mach number, air density, moment of inertia and centre of gravity, it calculates the rigid body stability derivatives. Figure 3.3 shows the modelled wing and tail of F25/UPWing in AVL.

⁵The aircraft model configuration used in this thesis will be discussed in detail in Section 3.4

Figure 3.3: The Wing and Tail of F25/UPWing modelled in AVL⁶

To automate the simulation process, a MATLAB script called "RB_AVL_extract.m" was implemented. This script executes the AVL directly from MATLAB and extracts the calculated rigid body stability derivatives required as input for the "aerodynamics.m" script calculations. The outputs of the two sub-functions "aerodynamics.m" and "propulsion.m", are then called during the "dynamics.m" function execution. Consequently, the output of the "dynamics.m" function is the X_p vector that contains the derivatives of the state variables. Furthermore, the state vector at trim conditions is calculated using the script "trim.m". In this script, the "dynamics.m" function is called, and the equations of motion are solved to trim the aircraft. Trim conditions mean that the aircraft is in a stationary state, and thus, all the time derivatives of the state variables implemented in the "dynamics.m" script are set to zero. This results in twelve equations with twelve unknowns. These equations are solved using the MATLAB function "fsolve". The "fsolve" function uses the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm to iteratively solve non-linear least squares problems [39]. For every iteration step, the "trim.m" script is called, which in turn calls the "dynamics.m" function. This continues until the equations are solved and the trim points can be found and saved in the state vector. For this trim routine, the state vector X is defined as:

$$X = [V, \theta, H, \alpha, q, \beta, r, \phi, p, \Psi, x_e, y_e], \quad (3.1)$$

⁶It should be noted that the wing is positioned in the middle; however, because it is on the negative side of the z-axis, it appears offset from this perspective. The Fig. A.1 in the appendix shows the same model from the top view, where the wing appears in the middle.

with the input vector U :

$$U = [m, x_{CG}, \delta_e, \delta_{ail1_r}, \delta_{ail1_l}, \delta_{ail2_r}, \delta_{ail2_l}, \delta_{outerflap_r}, \delta_{outerflap_l}, \delta_{innerflap_r}, \delta_{innerflap_l}, \delta_{flaperon_r}, \delta_{flaperon_l}, \delta_r, \delta_T, w_x, w_y, w_z], \quad (3.2)$$

and output vector Y , which in this case is equivalent to the state vector X . The terms x_e and y_e are the x and y trajectory coordinate in the IRF, respectively, while the other variables are already defined in Sec. 2.1. In addition, the input vector variables are represented as: δ_e the elevator deflection, δ_{ail1_r} and δ_{ail1_l} the inner aileron deflection, δ_{ail2_r} and δ_{ail2_l} the external aileron deflection, $\delta_{outerflap_r}$ and $\delta_{outerflap_l}$ the outerflap deflection, $\delta_{innerflap_r}$ and $\delta_{innerflap_l}$ the innerflap deflection, $\delta_{flaperon_r}$ and $\delta_{flaperon_l}$ the flaperon deflection, δ_r the rudder deflection, δ_T the throttle ratio and w_x , w_y and w_z are the wind components in IRF. Moreover, the indices r and l refer to the right and left control surfaces. As a further step, the state-space representation (see Eqs. 2.20 and 2.21) of the system is calculated by linearising around the trim condition in the "lin.m" function. In this context, the "dynamics.m" function is called in "lin.m" to set up the \underline{A} and \underline{B} matrices. Additionally, a function named "observation.m" was implemented to define the \underline{C} and \underline{D} matrices and also being called in the "lin.m" function. For the non-linearised system and for simulation purposes in Simulink, a "S-function" block is used. This block extends the capabilities of the Simulink environment by dynamically linking to subroutines that Matlab can automatically load and execute. In addition, the S-function can determine how a block operates during different parts of the simulation, such as initialisation, updates, outputs, and termination [40].

3.1.2 Aeroelastic Flight Dynamics Model Calculation with Quasi-Steady Aerodynamics

The calculation presented in this section is based on the equations of motion explained in Sec. 2.2. The flow chart for the flexible simulator with quasi-steady formulation differs from that of the rigid body simulator, as shown in Fig. 3.4. The implementation of the aeroelastic flight dynamics model requires several MATLAB scripts to be initialised in the "main.m" file. The first script, "<Aircraft Name>_Parameters.m", describes the same parameters as in the rigid body simulator, but with additional parameters that include the number of strips used for each lifting surface and the aerodynamic properties for each strip. As explained in Ch. 2, the lifting surfaces must be discretised into strips to apply the strip theory. Consequently, the lifting surfaces were discretised as presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: F25/UPWing Number of Strips for the Lifting Surfaces

Lifting Surfaces	Number of Strips
Wing	60
Horizontal Tail	20
Vertical Tail	14

The aerodynamic properties per strip are defined by extracting the aerodynamic coefficients along the span from AVL. Subsequently, the MATLAB function "spline" is used to create a polynomial function of each aerodynamic coefficient with respect to the y-position. The second script, "discretiza-

tion_aero.m", defines the width of each aerodynamic strip and the coordinates of the aerodynamic centre per strip. In a further step in the same script, the aerodynamic coefficients are calculated at the y-coordinates of the aerodynamic centre using the functions created by "spline" in "<Aircraft Name>_Parameters.m".

As mentioned earlier, calculating the aeroelastic flight dynamics model requires performing a modal analysis to obtain structural mode information. This analysis is executed in NASTRAN (a finite element model software) by applying SOL103. Then, an output file ".f06" is produced, which contains essential structural mode data. The German Aerospace Centre (DLR) performed this analysis for four different aircraft masses and provided the respective ".f06" files. For this methodology, the solution file used is "na_AircraftModel_GFEM_S103_modal_MZOAe.f06". To process this data points, the third script, "extract_NASTRAN_data.m" is responsible for extracting the structural modal properties such as eigenvalues, eigenvectors, structural node IDs, and their coordinates. In the provided modal analysis, the structural nodes are located on the load reference axis. In a subsequent step, interpolation is required to match the structural nodes with the aerodynamic centres. This is carried out in the "optlin.m" script.

The following steps in the simulator are analogous to the rigid body simulator, with differences in calculating aerodynamic forces and moments. In this regard, the aerodynamic forces and moments are function of the rigid body stability derivatives and the quasi-steady aerodynamic coefficients. These coefficients depend on the deformation of the lifting surfaces extracted from the structural modal analysis performed earlier. The calculation of these coefficients, as explained in [23], is implemented in the "flex_QS_calc.m" script. This script, along with "RB_AVL_extract.m", is then used as input in the "aerodynamics.m" script to calculate the aerodynamic forces and moments. Moreover, the state vector X also differs from that calculated in the rigid body simulator. In this case, the state vector X is defined as:

$$X = [V, \theta, H, \alpha, q, \beta, r, \phi, p, \Psi, x_e, y_e, \eta_i, \dot{\eta}_i], \quad (3.3)$$

where the terms η_i and $\dot{\eta}_i$ refer to the amplitudes of each elastic modal shape and their derivatives, while the index i represents the amount of modes. It should be noted that the input vector U is defined as in Eq. 3.2. Furthermore, for this flexible simulator version, the \underline{C} -matrix was augmented in the "observation.m" script to include the bending and torsion values of the chosen structural nodes of the lifting surfaces. This step is essential for animation purposes in a later step. Consequently, these values included in the output vector Y are presented as follows:

$$Y = [V, \theta, H, \alpha, q, \beta, r, \phi, p, \Psi, x_e, y_e, \eta_i, \dot{\eta}_i, \varphi_W, \gamma_W, \varphi_{HE}, \gamma_{HE}, \varphi_{VE}, \gamma_{VE}]. \quad (3.4)$$

The variables φ_W, γ_W represent the bending and torsion values for the wing, $\varphi_{HE}, \gamma_{HE}$ denote the bending and torsion values for the HE, and $\varphi_{VE}, \gamma_{VE}$ are the bending and torsion values of the VE. These terms are vectors, with each vector containing values corresponding to the number of chosen structural nodes. The nodes are selected to match the rigging elements position of the 3-D model in Blender.

Figure 3.4: Simplified Flow Chart of the Flexible Simulator for Quasi-Steady Aerodynamics

3.1.3 Aeroelastic Flight Dynamics Model Calculation with Unsteady Aerodynamics

The calculation discussed in this section is derived from the equations of motion described in Sec. 2.3. Figure 3.5 depicts a simplified flow chart of the flexible simulator based on the unsteady aerodynamics formulation. Comparing Fig. 3.4 with Fig. 3.5, it can be observed that the implementation steps for the aeroelastic flight dynamics model based on quasi-steady unsteady aerodynamics are identical except the "dynamics.m" script implementation. As illustrated in Fig. 3.5, the "dynamics.m" script includes two aerodynamics subfunctions: "aerodynamics_FoMo.m" and "aerodynamics_Q.m".

The "aerodynamics_FoMo.m" subfunction calculates aerodynamic forces and moments. It uses the rigid body coefficients extracted from "RB_AVL_extract.m" and the unsteady aerodynamic coefficients implemented in "flex_US_calc.m". These coefficients follow the formulation described in [25]. The second script, "aerodynamics_Q.m", calculates the generalised aerodynamic loads Q_{η_i} . According to Eq. 2.40, Q_{η_i} includes a component Q_{XU} , where X are the states and U are the inputs. The term Q_{XU} is derived from quasi-steady aerodynamic coefficients. Hence, "flex_QS_calc.m" is called within "aerodynamics_Q.m". In addition, Q_{η_i} is also a function of Q_{η_i} , $Q_{\dot{\eta}_i}$, and $Q_{\eta_{\lambda_i}}$ (see Eq. 2.41). These components rely on unsteady aerodynamic coefficients. Therefore, "flex_US_calc.m" is recalled within the "aerodynamics_Q.m" script.

The state vector X for this implementation routine is different and presented as follows:

$$X = [V, \theta, H, \alpha, q, \beta, r, \phi, p, \Psi, x_e, y_e, \eta_i, \dot{\eta}_i, \lambda_{1W}, \lambda_{2W}, \lambda_{1HE}, \lambda_{2HE}, \lambda_{1VE}, \lambda_{2VE}], \quad (3.5)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 represent the lag states as a consequence of the delay response of the aerodynamic lift. The indices W , HE and VE refer to the lifting surfaces: wing, HE and VE, respectively. These terms are vectors, which consist of as many values as the number of the aerodynamic strips. Furthermore, the input vector U is defined as in Eq. 3.2, while the output vector Y is equivalent to the state vector X .

Figure 3.5: Simplified Flow Chart of the Flexible Simulator for Unsteady Aerodynamics

3.1.4 Aeroelastic Flight Dynamics Model Simulation in Simulink

After the calculations are completed in MATLAB, the simulation is performed in Simulink. Figure 3.6 depicts a simplified presentation for the Simulink model implemented in this methodology. In this figure, the model components outside the dashed box are the same for the three modelling configurations (rigid body, quasi-steady, and unsteady). The difference lies in the dimension of the output vector Y . The input vector U remains consistent across all simulations. The dashed box represents additional blocks that are introduced only for animation purposes. In this methodology, the additional blocks are only incorporated for the quasi-steady aerodynamics simulation.

The model begins with the input vector U_{input} and the trim points vector U_{trim} , which are summed before being processed by the "S-function" block. The output vector of this block Y_{NL} represents the non-linear solution. The linear solution is simulated using the state-space simulink block, in which the \underline{A} , \underline{B} , \underline{C} and \underline{D} matrices are defined. The output of this block illustrates the linearised output vector Y_L .

The last two blocks represented in the dashed box are responsible for visualisation and the connection between Simulink and X-Plane. The "Geodetic Position" block, is a customised block that can be downloaded from [41]. It calculates the aircraft's geodetic position (latitude, longitude, altitude) based on the velocity components in the x , y , z directions (u , v , w) and the Euler angles (Φ , θ , Ψ). More information about the implementation of the geodetic position block can be found in [42], [43] and [44].

The "X-Plane Visualisation" block is another customised block. The components of this block are depicted in Fig. 3.7. The inputs for this block are the parameters sent to X-Plane for animation. These parameters are the deformation of the lifting surfaces (φ_W , γ_W , φ_{HE} , γ_{HE} , φ_{VE} , γ_{VE}) and the geodetic position of the aircraft. For animating the control surface deflection and thrust, the output vector Y in Eq. 3.4 should be further augmented to include the corresponding values as shown below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y = [& V, \theta, H, \alpha, q, \beta, r, \phi, p, \Psi, x_e, y_e, \eta_i, \dot{\eta}_i, \\
 & \varphi_W, \gamma_W, \varphi_{HE}, \gamma_{HE}, \varphi_{VE}, \gamma_{VE}, \\
 & \delta_e, \delta_{ail1_r}, \delta_{ail1_l}, \delta_{ail2_r}, \delta_{ail2_l}, \delta_{outerflap_r}, \delta_{outerflap_l}, \\
 & \delta_{innerflap_r}, \delta_{innerflap_l}, \delta_{flaperon_r}, \delta_{flaperon_l}, \delta_r, \delta_T].
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

Then, these input parameters are processed in several stages. First, the data is converted to double format, using "double" block. Afterwards, the data points are packed into bytes using the Simulink "Byte Pack" function. Finally, the packed data is transmitted via UDP using the Simulink "UDP Send" module. In this block, the port ID through which X-Plane can receive data must be specified, along with the IP address. If Simulink and X-Plane are running on the same computer, the IP address will be "127.0.0.1". The port ID can be found in X-Plane settings. It should be noted that the "UDP Send" block will not function without an implemented plug-in, that allows data transfer from Simulink to X-Plane.

Figure 3.6: Simplified Presentation of Simulink Model

Figure 3.7: Simplified Presentation of X-Plane Visualisation Block

3.2 Visualisation

The visualisation process involves creating a detailed visual presentation of the aircraft model, which enables comprehensive simulation and analysis in a virtual environment. The following subsections describe each step in this process.

3.2.1 3-D Modelling in Blender

The aircraft model used in this work is modelled using the Airbus A321 neo as a reference. In this regard, an A320 model was used [45] and then extensively modified. Figure 3.8 shows the original model. This model was not rigged or animated and lacked texture and UV⁷ mapping, as mentioned in [45].

Figure 3.8: The Original Airbus A320 Model presented in Blender

The first step of modifying the original 3-D model was the rigging process. Rigging is a process of creating the skeletal structure of a 3-D model to enable animation. This process involves constructing a system of bones and joints, known as rig elements, which can be manipulated to control the movement of the 3-D model. For this aircraft, all the control surfaces had to be rigged, which involved first selecting and separating all the control surfaces individually, as they were not distinct in the original model. The skeletal structure of the control surfaces was achieved by adding an empty plain axis to represent the hinge axes of the control surfaces, such as the left elevator shown in Figure 3.9. In Figure 3.9a, the empty plain axis is represented in yellow, while the elevator is highlighted in orange. This empty plain axis was then parented to the control surface, making the empty plain axis the *parent* and the control surface the *child*, as illustrated in Figure 3.9b. The hierarchy shows that "hinge_elevator_left" is on a higher level than "elevator_left". Thus, when the *parent* (hinge axis)

⁷The process of creating a 2-D image of a 3-D object

moves, the *child* (control surface) follows. This process was repeated for all control surfaces.

Figure 3.9: Rigging and Parenting Strategy for Left Elevator in Blender

The wing of the original model did not match the wing used in this work. Therefore, the required wing configuration was modelled in OpenVSP. The wing was divided into sixteen sections, eight sections per side, to ensure that each control surface was allocated its own section, which would facilitate the parenting process of the flexible wing that would come as a subsequent step. Parameters such as root chord, tip chord, sweep angle, and dihedral angle were specified for each section, and the corresponding profile data were also provided. Figure 3.10 shows the modelled wing after modelling it in OpenVSP. Afterwards, the wing model was exported from OpenVSP as an ".obj" file and imported into Blender. Then, the same rigging and animation process for the control surfaces was repeated for the new wing.

Figure 3.10: Modelled Wing of the Aircraft F25/UPWing in OpenVSP

To rig and animate the aircraft for flexible motion, the wing, the horizontal tail plane, and the vertical tail plane were considered. For the wing that had been divided into eight sections per side, each section was selected, separated, and then rigged. In this case, the rigging elements used were bones. Each section of the wing was rigged with two bones placed at the same location. One bone was responsible for the bending motion and the other for the torsional motion.

The bending bone was set as the *parent* to its corresponding section. If a section includes a hinge axis of a control surface, the bending bone was set as the *parent* to both the section and the hinge axis, as shown in Figure 3.11. Figure 3.11a illustrates the rig element used while Figure 3.11b clarifies the parenting setup. In Figure 3.11a, the section was cut and separated and the bone was used as a rig element. The *parent* element is highlighted in yellow (bone), while the *child* elements (wing section and hinge axis of the outer flap) are marked in orange. Figure 3.11b shows the sequence of parenting, where the bone responsible for the bending of the left wing section 3, labelled as "deflection03_left", is the *parent* of both the section labelled as "wing03_left" and the hinge axis of the outer flap labelled as "hinge_outerflap_left". On the other hand, "hinge_outerflap_left" is the *parent* of the control surface "outerflap_left", forming a parenting chain.

(a) Rigging Elements used in Blender

(b) Parenting Strategy used in Blender

Figure 3.11: Rigging and Parenting Strategy for Left Wing Section No. 3 with the Outer Flap in Blender

The next step involved establishing the parenting hierarchy. The torsion bone was parented to the deflection (bending) bone, and each bone of a section was parented to the adjacent section's bone. Figure 3.12 illustrates the parenting strategy for one side of the wing. As shown in the figure, the parenting sequence begins from the tip of the wing section numbered (n) and continues until reaching the root wing section numbered (n-7). The "Torsion (n)" bone is the *parent* of "Deflection (n)", the "Deflection (n-1)" bone is the *parent* of "Torsion (n)", "Torsion (n-1)" is the *parent* of "Deflection (n-1)", and so forth, until reaching the last root section bone "Torsion (n-7)", which is the *parent* of "Deflection (n-7)". Since one side of the wing has eight sections, n is 8, making n-7 refer to the first section of that side. The same strategy applies to the other side of the wing.

Figure 3.12: Parenting Strategy in Blender for One Side of the Wing

When an element that is already a *parent* becomes a *child* to another element, all its *child* elements will also inherit the movements not only of their *parent* but also the motion of the *parent* of their *parent*. This is what the braces refer to in the previous Fig. 3.12. This means, if "Torsion (1)" at the root of the wing is rotated, wing sections from 2 to 8 will rotate relative to it, and if, for example, bone "Torsion (3)" rotates, all wing sections from 4 to 8 will also rotate relative to this and so on. By this method of parenting, smooth motion is enabled, and each bone can be given an independent value, but at the same time, the *child* bones will rotate and deform relative to their defined *parent*.

Analogous to the wing, the horizontal tail and the vertical tail were also prepared for animation to simulate their deformation. The horizontal tail was divided into four sections, two sections for each side. For the vertical tail, using only one section was sufficient, so it was not divided.

The final result of the rigging and animation of the aircraft with the newly modelled wing is shown in Figure 3.13. The aircraft is shown twice: Once with colour shading to distinguish the separated sections of the wing and the control surfaces (Figure 3.13a), and once with white shading (Figure 3.13b). Both figures are presented from different perspectives to demonstrate the deformation from various angles.

(a) With Coloured Shading

(b) With White Shading

Figure 3.13: Animated Flexible Aircraft in Blender

The last step in Blender is to prepare the model for direct import into PlaneMaker/X-Plane. For this purpose, the X-Plane developers offer an add-on called "xplane2blender" [46], which, despite its name, is responsible for preparing the model from Blender to X-Plane. By installing this add-on in Blender, additional options will appear. The first option, shown in Figure 3.14, allows the user to add "Datarefs" in Blender. "Datarefs" are names of data or objects defined by X-Plane. For example, if the user assigns the name "sim/flightmodel/controls/ail1_def" to a specific object in Blender, X-Plane will recognise it as an aileron, and the movement of the aileron will follow the animation set in Blender, allowing the aileron to move only up and down. All the "Datarefs" offered by X-Plane, along with their descriptions and units, can be found in [47].

Figure 3.14: X-Plane Toolbar in Blender

The second important option, appears in the tool bar in this path: File → Export → X-Plane Object (.obj) in Blender. The option to export the model as "X-Plane Object (.obj)", which is responsible for converting the Blender data into an ".obj" file that X-Plane can recognise.

3.2.2 Texturing in Armorpaint

In this step, the aircraft was painted. To paint a 3-D model, a software is required that can create a 2-D image from a 3-D surface. Blender can be used for this purpose, but the "xplane2blender" add-on does not allow exporting the texture with the model. Therefore, the ArmorPaint programme was used.

In ArmorPaint, the aircraft can be imported as an ".obj" file, and then the user can paint the aircraft. Consequently, ArmorPaint generates a 2-D image from this painting. For this purpose, the aircraft was divided into several parts, and each part was exported separately from Blender as an ".obj" file and imported into ArmorPaint. Figure 3.15 shows examples of images produced by ArmorPaint. Figure 3.15a represents the 2-D image for the engine's painting surface, while Figure 3.15b illustrates the 2-D image for the fuselage surface.

Figure 3.15: 2-D Images generated from ArmorPaint

3.2.3 Importing in PlaneMaker/X-Plane

As a next step, the images generated from ArmorPaint, along with the "X-Plane Object (.obj)" files exported from Blender, were imported into PlaneMaker. The typical process for animating a custom-designed aircraft in X-Plane involves first creating the 3-D model in Blender. Since Blender offers advanced options for the rigging and animation process. Subsequently, the same aircraft must be modelled in PlaneMaker, as PlaneMaker works as the source of physical parameters for X-Plane. In PlaneMaker, modelling the aircraft not only involves defining geometrical parameters but also requires input of the physical configuration data such as weight, thrust, CG among other parameters. Once this is accomplished, the user hides any geometric parts produced by PlaneMaker, and the aircraft is flown using the 3-D model created in Blender along with the X-Plane physics engine, which relies on the data provided in PlaneMaker. However, for this work, modelling the aircraft in PlaneMaker was not required because the X-Plane physics engine was turned off. Consequently, PlaneMaker was used only to create the ".acf" file, which is the format necessary for importation into X-Plane. After creating this file, the aircraft can be found in the X-Plane aircraft menu. Figure 3.16 shows the F25/UPWing aircraft with texturing on the ground in X-Plane.

Figure 3.16: F25/UPWing Aircraft in X-Plane

3.2.4 Plug-in for Simulink and X-Plane Interaction

This Section describes a custom plug-in designed to enable X-Plane to receive and apply real-time data from Simulink to the modelled aircraft. The plug-in consists of seven main functions.

The function "dataReady" is responsible for unpacking the bytes received from Simulink into float or double values. This ensures that the data are in the correct format for further processing.

To connect a customised plug-in with X-Plane, the Software Developers Kit (SDK) plug-in must be downloaded from [48]. This plug-in, developed by X-Plane developers, enables users to create extensions that can operate and communicate with X-Plane. More information can be found in [48] and [49]. A customised plug-in must include five essential callbacks: "XPluginStart", "XPluginStop", "XPluginEnable", "XPluginDisable", and "XPluginReceiveMessage" [49].

The "XPluginStart" function is called when the custom plug-in is started. Within this function, the necessary "Datarefs" for the project are defined. For these "Datarefs" to receive values from Simulink, they must be writable. However, if X-Plane has implemented a "Dataref" as read-only, it cannot be overwritten. To solve this, custom "Datarefs" were created and registered using the function "XPLMRegisterDataAccessor" in the "XPluginStart" function. Additionally, the port through which X-Plane receives data must be specified here.

On the other hand, the "XPluginStop" function is activated when the custom plug-in stops. It is important to unregister the custom datarefs in this function using "XPLMUnregisterDataAccessor" to prevent conflicts and inaccuracies caused by interfering "Datarefs" from X-Plane and the custom

"Datarefs".

The functions "XPluginEnable" and "XPluginDisable" are responsible for enabling and disabling the custom plug-in, respectively. It is important to distinguish between these functions and the start/stop functions. "XPluginEnable" and "XPluginDisable" control the activation state of the plug-in, whereas "XPluginStart" and "XPluginStop" manage the operational state within the simulation. Therefore, while the plug-in can be enabled or disabled once, it can be started and stopped multiple times during the same session.

For sending messages to the customised plug-in, "XPluginReceiveMessage" is implemented, allowing X-Plane to send the plug-in messages or notifications such as an aircraft crash or the selection of a new aircraft model.

Finally, an additional callback, "MyFlightLoopCallback", is implemented to set and update the values of the "Datarefs" in "XPluginStart" to the values received and unpacked in the "dataReady" function for each time frame. This function ensures that the real-time data from Simulink is continuously updated and applied to the aircraft model in X-Plane, enabling accurate and dynamic simulation.

3.3 Summarised Steps (User Guide)

This section outlines the summarised steps to provide an overview of how to use the tool and apply it to other aircraft models. The steps are as follows:

1. Creation of a 3-D Model: Create the 3-D model either directly in Blender or by modelling the aircraft in OpenVSP and exporting it as an ".obj" file, which can then be imported into Blender.
2. Rigging and Animating: Rig and animate the 3-D model in Blender.
3. Installation of xplane2blender: Download the "xplane2blender" add-on and install it in Blender.
4. Defining X-Plane Datarefs: Define the X-Plane Datarefs in Blender.
5. Exporting the Model: Export the animated 3-D model with the defined Datarefs from Blender as an "X-Plane Object (.obj)".
6. Creating Aircraft Folder in X-Plane: Create a new folder in the X-Plane directory at the path: X-Plane → Aircraft → [aircraft folder name]. In this folder, the user can save any customised aircraft.
7. Importing into PlaneMaker: Import the "X-Plane Object (.obj)" into PlaneMaker.
8. Saving 3-D Model in PlaneMaker: Save the file "X-Plane Object (.obj)" in PlaneMaker as an ".acf" file.
9. Painting the Aircraft (Optional Step): Paint the aircraft using ArmorPaint or similar software. It is highly recommended to export each part of the aircraft from Blender as separate ".obj" files to facilitate easier painting in ArmorPaint.

10. Saving 2-D Images: Save the 2-D images exported from ArmorPaint in the same aircraft folder created earlier in the X-Plane director.
11. Implementing the Plug-in.
12. Compiling the Plug-in: Compile the plug-in to create an ".xpl" file.
13. Importing the ".xpl" File: Import the ".xpl" file into the X-Plane directory at the path: X-Plane → Resources → plugins.

It should be noted that the plug-in can be implemented in any programming language. In this case, the programming language used is C++. After implementation, the plug-in should be compiled to create the ".xpl" file. This compilation process converts the implemented code into machine language, which X-Plane can interpret. For more detailed information on implementing the code, refer to Sec. 3.2.4.

3.4 Case Study

The DLR in Hamburg designed a virtual aircraft named DLR-F25 for research purposes. This aircraft, modelled after the Airbus A321neo, features a HAR wing. The DLR-F25 model is employed in the UP-Wing Project, which focusses on investigating wing technologies that can contribute in reducing CO_2 emissions and that can be applied to the next generation of short- and medium-range transport aircraft [5]. In this context, the new wing model was optimised by the Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology from the DLR in Braunschweig. Since the wing of DLR-F25 has been replaced by the wing of the UP-Wing project, the name "F25/UPWing" is used in this work to refer to the UP-Wing Project aircraft.

The technical information regarding the main geometric and performance data of F25/UPWing used for visualisation and the flight dynamics model, is presented in Table 3.2. It can be seen from the table that the F25/UPWing is designed to fly with a cruise Mach number of 0.78, at a cruise altitude of 10,258.5347 meters. It is to be pointed out, that the mass of the aircraft used for the calculations is the zero fuel mass and not the cruise mass⁸. The wing was designed with a high aspect ratio. Moreover, the wing design includes 40 different profiles, enclosing those of the control surfaces. The control surfaces are inner flaps, flaperon, outer flaps, and two ailerons. On the other hand, the profiles used for both the horizontal tail and the vertical tail are NACA009. In addition, the institute of aeroelastic from DLR Göttingen provided a structural modal of the entire aircraft. To visualise a structural model a ".bdf" file is required. In this work the ".bdf" file used is the "na_AircraftModel_GFEM_S103_modal_MZOae_aio.bdf". Figure 3.17 shows the FEM of F25/UPWing visualised using Patran software⁹.

⁸During the work on this thesis, the cruise mass had not yet been identified. Therefore, it was decided to work with the zero fuel mass.

⁹Patran is a platform designed for both the preparation and analysis stages of Finite Element Analysis (FEA) [50]

Table 3.2: F25/UPWing Technical Data used for the Simulation Tool

Parameter Name	Symbol	Value
Cruise Mach Number	Ma	0.78
Cruise Altitude	H	10,258.5347 m
Cruise Mass	$m_{MZO A}$	75,036.6 kg
Horizontal Tail Span	b_h	13.3720 m
Horizontal Tail Surface Area	S_h	28.83085 m^2
Vertical Tail Span	b_v	6.79035 m
Vertical Tail Surface Area	S_v	27.527399865 m^2
Central Gravity Position	CG	[20.05 0 -0.078293]
Max. Thrust	F_{max}	119114.9 N
Inertia Moment about CG	I_{xx}	8.955113E+05 $kg.m^2$
Inertia Moment about CG	I_{yy}	6.806891E+06 $kg.m^2$
Inertia Moment about CG	I_{zz}	7.573854E+06 $kg.m^2$
Inertia Moment about CG	I_{xz}	2.469352E+05 $kg.m^2$
Inertia Moment about CG	I_{xy}	1.841769E-05 $kg.m^2$
Inertia Moment about CG	I_{yz}	-5.069001E+00 $kg.m^2$

Figure 3.17: Finite Element Model of F25/UPWing Aircraft

4 | Results

This chapter presents the simulation results of the F25/UPWing using the animation outputs generated by the tool developed based on the methodology explained in Ch. 3. The investigation begins with a stability analysis. Then, the analysis extends to include both time- and frequency-domain simulations for the three aerodynamic models: Rigid body, quasi-steady, and unsteady. It should be pointed out that the animation tool is employed exclusively for the quasi-steady approach, as the unsteady calculation requires a considerable processing time, making real-time animation impractical.

4.1 Stability Analysis

In this section, a dynamic response analysis of the F25/UPWing aircraft is provided. The examination includes a presentation of the zero-map for the three aerodynamic models. Moreover, a comparison of the frequencies and damping of the flexible modes and the rigid body modes is discussed. In addition, the comparison extends to include the trim conditions. To ensure clarity in understanding the structural modes considered in this analysis, the section begins with a description of the shape of these modes. As explained in Sec. 3.1.2, calculating an aeroelastic flight dynamics model requires a modal analysis as an initial step. The solution sequence SOL 103 from Nastran provides 56 modes, including the first 6 rigid body modes for the 6 DOF of the structure. However, in the present thesis, the focus is on the first five structural modes to facilitate real-time animation. Given that the calculation time increases with the amount of modes, which can impact the efficiency of the animation tool.

4.1.1 Flexible Modes

Figure 4.1 illustrates the first five elastic modes shape for the F25/UPWing aircraft visualised in "Patran". Mode 1, displayed in Fig. 4.1a, represents a coupling between the first bending mode and the torsion mode. However, the first bending mode is predominant, with only a minor torsional component. This mode is mainly characterised by a symmetric wing bending at a frequency of 2.31 Hz. Mode 2, shown in Fig. 4.1b, depicts the second bending mode with a small torsional influence, highlighting the asymmetric wing bending at 2.76 Hz. Mode 3, illustrated in Fig. 4.1c, shows a coupling between wing first bending, wing torsion, fuselage deformation and engine motion, occurring at a frequency of 3.19 Hz. Fig. 4.1d presents mode 4, which exhibits a coupling between wing second bending, wing torsion, and fuselage torsional motion, at a frequency of 3.46 Hz. Lastly, mode 5, depicted in Fig. 4.1e, demonstrates a complex coupling between the first bending of the wing, the

torsion motion of the wing, the engine deformation and the deformation of the fuselage, occurring at a frequency of 3.97 Hz. A summarised table for the elastic modes with their frequencies and mode shape description can be found in the appendix in Tab. A.1.

Figure 4.1: F25/UPWing First Five Elastic Mode Shapes

Figure 4.2 depicts the pole-zero map for the three flight dynamics models: Rigid body, quasi-steady, and unsteady. As shown in the figure, it can be concluded that the aircraft is stable because all the eigenvalues are located on the negative side of the zero map. Furthermore, the unsteady flight dynamics model includes more states than that of the quasi-steady or the rigid body models. Specifically, the unsteady model incorporates the rigid body states, the first five elastic modes, and the states corresponding to the aerodynamic lag. The quasi-steady model includes the rigid body states and the first five elastic modes, while the rigid body model includes only the rigid body states. Moreover, the same figure shows that the frequency differences of the elastic modes between the quasi-steady and unsteady approaches are minimal. Modes 1, 2, 4, and 5 exhibit nearly identical frequencies with minimal deviation in damping in both the quasi-steady and unsteady models. In contrast, mode 3 shows slight deviation, with the quasi-steady model exhibiting a higher frequency and slightly increased damping compared to the unsteady model. In Addition, Tab. 4.1 provides a comparison with the exact values of the frequencies and damping for the first five elastic modes.

Figure 4.2: F25/UPWing Pole-Zero Map for the Dynamics of RB, QS and US at $Ma = 0.78$ Table 4.1: F25/UPWing Aeroelastic Modes Comparison for $Ma = 0.78$

AE Modes	QS	US
$\omega_{n_{\eta_1}}$ [rad/sec]	18.6	18.8
ξ_{η_1}	0.304	0.248
$\omega_{n_{\eta_2}}$ [rad/sec]	19.6	19.8
ξ_{η_2}	0.0506	0.0578
$\omega_{n_{\eta_3}}$ [rad/sec]	21.2	20.7
ξ_{η_3}	0.204	0.17
$\omega_{n_{\eta_4}}$ [rad/sec]	21.7	21.7
ξ_{η_4}	0.0314	0.0334
$\omega_{n_{\eta_5}}$ [rad/sec]	25.1	25
ξ_{η_5}	0.0247	0.0239

4.1.2 Rigid Body Modes

Analogous to the frequency comparison of the first five elastic modes, a comparison of the rigid body modes for the three aerodynamic models is illustrated in Fig. 4.3. This figure provides a zoomed-in view of Fig. 4.2 to highlight the rigid body modes. It can be concluded that the eigenvalues deviation between the quasi-steady and unsteady approaches are negligible for the five rigid body modes, with the exception of the Phugoid mode, which exhibits a minimal deviation. Additionally, small deviations are observed between the rigid body and the flexible flight dynamics for the Short period and Spiral modes. Moreover, the highest damping for the Phugoid and Dutch roll modes are observed in the quasi-steady approach. For a precise presentation, the frequencies and damping values of the five rigid body modes for the three flight dynamics modelling techniques are summarised in Tab. 4.2.

Figure 4.3: F25/UPWing Pole-Zero Map for the Dynamics RB, QS and US at $Ma = 0.78$ (Zoomed in)

Table 4.2: F25/UPWing Rigid Body Modes Comparison for $Ma = 0.78$

Eigenmodes	RB	QS	US
$\omega_{n_{Ph}}$ [rad/sec]	0.0661	0.0677	0.0674
ξ_{Ph}	0.03	0.0497	0.0367
$\omega_{n_{SP}}$ [rad/sec]	2.12	1.97	1.97
ξ_{SP}	0.256	0.24	0.24
$\omega_{n_{DR}}$ [rad/sec]	1.35	1.37	1.37
ξ_{DR}	0.0444	0.0493	0.046
ω_{n_R} [rad/sec]	4.11	2.34	2.35
ξ_R	1	1	1
ω_{n_S} [rad/sec]	0.00522	0.00875	0.00865
ξ_S	1	1	1

4.1.3 Trim Conditions

Table 4.3 presents the trim points for the three models. The trim points for the quasi-steady and unsteady approaches are nearly identical. However, the angle of attack required for both the quasi-steady and unsteady models is higher than the angle of attack needed for the rigid body model to achieve the trimmed condition for the aircraft. Due to the torsion of the wing, the lift force decreases. Therefore, a higher angle of attack is needed for flexible aircraft to generate a lifting force that can compensate the weight of the aircraft. Furthermore, a comparison of the thrust values reveals that the quasi-steady and unsteady models require more thrust to trim the aircraft compared to the rigid body model. This is due to the higher angle of attack, which leads to a higher induced drag. As a result, a greater thrust for compensation is required. However, there is a deviation in the thrust trim values between the quasi-steady and unsteady models. This discrepancy cannot be explained based on the current analysis, indicating the need for further investigation and review of the quasi-steady model. It was initially expected that the thrust trim values of the quasi-steady and unsteady models would be identical. Furthermore, the table shows that the unsteady approach has more states than the quasi-steady approach. These extra states in the unsteady model refer to the amplitude of the aerodynamic lag. The aerodynamic lag is calculated for the wing, the horizontal tail, and the vertical tail for each strip per each lift surface.

Table 4.3: F25/UPWing Trim Points Comparison for $Ma = 0.78$

	RB	QS	US
Θ [°]	0.96405	1.9861	1.9815
α [°]	0.96405	1.9861	1.9815
Φ [°]	0	0	0
Thrust [N]	40757.134	53922.961	45732.455
δ_e [°]	0.075	-0.816	-0.766
δ_{ail2r} [°]	0	0.001	0.001
δ_{ail2l} [°]	0	-0.001	-0.001
δ_r [°]	0	0.0012	0.0013
η_1 [-]	-	-22.5045	-22.4733
η_2 [-]	-	0.0023	0.0023
η_3 [-]	-	-2.7988	-2.7761
η_4 [-]	-	0.0033	0.0033
η_5 [-]	-	-2.7035	-2.6977
$\dot{\eta}_1$ [-]	-	-2.58E-16	-1.76E-18
$\dot{\eta}_2$ [-]	-	-1.28E-15	-6.49E-15
$\dot{\eta}_3$ [-]	-	-7.96E-15	4.38E-18
$\dot{\eta}_4$ [-]	-	3.82E-18	7.11E-15
$\dot{\eta}_5$ [-]	-	-4.51E-14	-9.57E-18
λ_{1_w} [-]	-	-	[-4.52E-17,...,4.52E-17]
λ_{2_w} [-]	-	-	[-1.01E-17,...,1.01E-17]
$\lambda_{1_{ne}}$ [-]	-	-	[-1.73E-19,...,1.31E-19]
$\lambda_{2_{ne}}$ [-]	-	-	[-4.501E-20,...,3.41E-20]
$\lambda_{1_{ve}}$ [-]	-	-	[5.02E-17,...,1.31E-17]
$\lambda_{2_{ve}}$ [-]	-	-	[1.31E-17,...,2.28E-17]

4.2 Rigid Body Flight Dynamics Simulations

In this section, the results of the rigid body simulation are presented. The simulation is performed according to the methodology illustrated in Ch. 3.1.1. As explained in this chapter, the calculation of the rigid body model requires the computation of rigid body derivatives as an initial step. This step is performed using AVL, and the resulting derivatives are summarised in the appendix in Tabs. A.2 and A.3. For the rigid body dynamics analysis, two simulations are conducted in the time domain, as shown in Tab. 4.4. An elevator doublet is used as an input to excite the longitudinal motion, while the lateral motion is stimulated using a doublet in the rudder.

Table 4.4: Time-Domain Simulations for the Rigid Body Flight Dynamics Model

Motion	Input	Control Surface
Longitudinal	Doublet 5°	Elevator
Lateral	Doublet 5°	Rudder

4.2.1 Longitudinal Dynamics of the Rigid Body Flight Dynamics Model

Figure 4.4 illustrates the longitudinal states response for the rigid body configuration to an elevator doublet input of 5 degrees. A positive elevator command indicates a downward deflection, leading to increased lift on the horizontal tail. This results in a pitch-down moment. Consequently, the nose of the aircraft goes down, leading to an increase in velocity, as shown in Fig. 4.4a. Simultaneously, the altitude decreases, as depicted in Fig. 4.4b. The pitch-down moment also causes a decrease in the angle of attack and the pitch rate, as illustrated in Figs. 4.4c and 4.4d respectively. As the pitch-down motion decreases the lift force relative to the aircraft's weight, the load factor also decreases, as shown in Fig. 4.4e. Furthermore, the longitudinal states response demonstrates the stability of the aircraft (see Fig. 4.3), since it can be observed that after stimulating the longitudinal motion, the aircraft returns to the trim condition. In addition, from Fig. 4.4, it can be concluded that the longitudinal states response for both linear and non-linear systems are almost identical. Further explanation about the linearisation process can be found in Sec. 2.1.

Figure 4.4: F25/UPWing RB Longitudinal Response for Elevator Doublet Input with 5 Degrees

4.2.2 Lateral Dynamics of the Rigid Body Flight Dynamics Model

Figure 4.5 depicts the lateral states response for the rigid body configuration to a rudder doublet input of 5 degrees. According to [51], a positive rudder command results in a control surface deflection to the right considering the aircraft from behind. This deflection generates a left side force, which consequently produces a positive yaw moment. This positive yaw moment leads to a positive heading angle, as shown in Figure 4.5a, and a positive yaw rate, as illustrated in Figure 4.5b. Furthermore, this side force has a distance from the CG of the aircraft leading to a positive roll moment, which subsequently leads to a positive bank angle, as shown in Fig. 4.5c, and a positive roll rate, as depicted in Fig. 4.5d. Additionally, the sideslip angle decreases, as illustrated in Figure 4.5e. It should be pointed out that the bank angle and the roll rate response to the rudder command exhibit a non-minimum phase characteristic, resulting in a delayed response to the rudder input. Therefore, with a positive yaw rate, the initial response of the aircraft is to roll to the left first before reacting to the input of the rudder and yaw to the right. This non-minimum phase can be observed in the pole-zero map in the appendix in Fig. A.2. Moreover, Fig. 4.5 shows that the response of the later states for the linear and non-linear systems are almost the same. Furthermore, in the same figure the stability of the lateral dynamic response can also be observed, as the aircraft tends to return to the trim condition. However, the dynamic response in Fig. 4.4 is higher damped than that in Fig. 4.5. To analyse this, the damping values in Tab. 4.2 should be referenced. When the lateral motion is excited using rudder input, the most dominant motion detected in the response is the Dutch roll motion. While exciting the longitudinal motion with the elevator input, a response dominated by the Short period motion is induced. By comparing the damping values of the Dutch roll motion and the Short period motion, it can be concluded that the Short period motion exhibits higher damping than the Dutch roll motion.

Figure 4.5: F25/UPWing RB Lateral Response for Rudder Doublet Input with 5 Degrees

4.3 Quasi-Steady Flexible Dynamics Simulations

This section presents the simulation results of the quasi-steady model, including animation outputs from X-Plane¹⁰. The evaluation begins with an eigenvector analysis. This analysis facilitates the determination of which states contribute to which eigenvalues. Consequently, it becomes easier to identify the elastic modes expected to be excited by longitudinal motion and those by lateral motion. For the time-domain analysis, the simulation studies presented in Tab. 4.5 are carried out. For longitudinal motion, a doublet input with 10 degrees in the elevator and a chirp with 15 degrees are performed. For lateral motion, a 10 degree doublet in the aileron and rudder, as well as a step input in the aileron, are applied.

Table 4.5: Time-Domain Simulations for the Quasi-Steady Flexible Flight Dynamics Model

Motion	Input	Control Surface
Longitudinal	Doublet 10°	Elevator
Longitudinal	Chirp 15°	Elevator
Lateral	Doublet 10°	Rudder
Lateral	Doublet 10°	Aileron
Lateral	Step 1°	Aileron

The time-domain simulation results include presentations of both the dynamic response and the structural response. It is important to note that the structural response figures are depicted in the structural coordinate system, where x points to the fuselage, y to the right, and z upward. Additionally, it should be noted that the starting point of the aircraft before any excitation is the trimmed condition. The aircraft in its trimmed condition already exhibits wing deformation and torsion. Therefore, any structural analysis in this chapter considers variations in the lift force from this initial state. Figure 4.6 represents the X-Plane animation result of the aircraft F25/UPWing in the trimmed condition, where the wing deforms upward in the z-axis and rotates downward around the y-axis.

¹⁰For all the animations presented in this chapter, corresponding videos have been recorded and included as supplementary material with this thesis.

Figure 4.6: X-Plane Animation Result of F25/UPWing in the Trimmed Condition

4.3.1 Eigenvector Analysis

Figure 4.7 depicts the eigenvector analysis for the F25/UPWing at $Ma = 0.78$ and $H = 10258.5m$. This eigenvector analysis is equivalent to the Modal Assurance Criteria (MAC) map. The figure illustrates the degree of consistency between a normalised mode and a system state. The colour bar, which varies between values 0 and 1, represents the degree of correlation. For example, values close to 1 demonstrate that the normalised mode is highly coupled with a particular system state, whereas values close to 0 indicate a weak coupling. Furthermore, the y-axis represents the rigid body states: Velocity V , altitude H , pitch rate q , yaw rate r , roll rate p , pitch angle Θ , angle of attack α , sideslip angle β , roll angle Φ ; and the states of the first five structural modes η and their derivatives $\dot{\eta}$. The x-axis illustrates the rigid body modes (Short period, Roll, Dutch roll, Spiral, and Phugoid) and the structural modes (Mode 1, Mode 2, Mode 3, Mode 4, and Mode 5).

Considering the rigid body modes, both longitudinal and lateral motions can be observed. For longitudinal motion, the coupling between velocity V and altitude H is evident, indicating the phugoid mode. In addition, there is a coupling between pitch angle Θ , angle of attack α , and pitch rate q , which refers to the Short period mode. In lateral motion, the correlation between roll angle ϕ and yaw angle ψ reveals the Spiral motion. Furthermore, the strong participation of yaw rate r , roll rate p , side slip angle β , bank angle Φ , and yaw angle ψ signifies the Dutch roll motion. The interaction between roll rate p and bank angle Φ indicates the roll motion. Moreover, the minor Dutch roll component in the Roll motion is represented by the weak correlation of yaw rate r with roll rate p and bank angle Φ .

Regarding the coupling between rigid body modes and structural modes, the analysis reveals a significant coupling between the Short period mode and the structural mode shape η_1 , with a correlation value of 0.43. Moreover, the Short period exhibits a minor coupling with mode shape η_5 , which has a correlation value of 0.15. Furthermore, there is a coupling between the Dutch roll mode and the modal shapes η_2 and η_4 . The coupling between the Dutch roll and η_4 is higher than that of η_2 . The Roll motion indicates coupling with the structural mode η_2 and an even higher coupling with the structural mode η_4 , which has a correlation value of 0.62.

Figure 4.7: F25/UPWing Eigenvector Analysis at Ma=0.78

4.3.2 Longitudinal Dynamics of the Quasi-Steady Flexible Dynamics Model

Elevator Doublet Input

Figure 4.8 illustrates the longitudinal states response to a doublet elevator command of 10 degrees. As shown in this figure, the longitudinal states react as previously described in Sec. 4.2.1. A positive elevator deflection results in an increase in velocity, a decrease in altitude, a reduction in angle of attack, a decrease in pitch rate, and a decrease in load factor. Analogously to the rigid body response, the longitudinal states response for the quasi-steady model is followed by aircraft stabilisation and a return to the trim condition. In addition, the response of the linearised system is almost aligned with that of the non-linear system.

Figure 4.9 shows the wing tip deformation in response to the elevator command. A positive elevator command generates an upward lift force on the horizontal tail and a downward lift force on the wing, leading to a pitch-down moment. This reduction in the lift force of the wing due to the new aerodynamic load generated from the elevator input, causes the wing to deform downward in the z -axis, as illustrated in Fig. 4.9a. Consequently, this lift force induces a moment that causes the wing to twist upwards around the y -axis, as shown in Fig. 4.9b. In addition, it can be observed from Fig. 4.9a, that the highest wing tip deformation for this simulation reaches almost 20 %.

The structural response of the horizontal tail is represented in Fig.4.9c and 4.9d. The increase in the lifting force on the horizontal tail due to the elevator input results in upward deformation in the z -axis, as depicted in Fig. 4.9c. This force also induces a moment that causes the tail to rotate downward around the y -axis, as shown in Fig. 4.9d. On the other hand, the structural response contribution of the vertical tail to this simulation is nearly zero, as indicated in Figs. 4.9e and 4.9f.

Figure 4.8: F25/UPWing QS Longitudinal Response for Elevator Doublet Input with 10 Degrees

Figure 4.9: F25/UPWing QS Structural Response for Elevator Doublet Input with 10 Degrees

Figure 4.9 shows a phase shift in the wing tip response to the elevator command. This phase shift is further illustrated in the Bode diagram in Fig. 4.10. As shown in this figure, within the frequency range, where the elastic modes are located, the phase shift varies between -142° to -360° . Observing the structural response to this simulation, it can be concluded, that the dominant elastic mode excited is Mode 1, which is a coupling between symmetric bending and torsion. According to the Bode diagram, this mode has a phase shift of -142° with respect to the elevator command.

Figure 4.10: Bode Diagram Elevator Command to Left Wing Tip Displacement

Figures 4.11 and 4.12 represent the animation results from X-Plane. Figure 4.11 illustrates the aircraft's response at $t = 2s$. As depicted, the nose pitches downward while the wing deforms downward and rotates upward. Figure 4.12 shows the animation results at $t = 3s$, where the aircraft's nose pitches upward, and the wing tip deformation is upward and rotating downward. By comparing Figs. 4.11 and 4.12 with Fig. 4.9, it can be concluded that the animation tool successfully represents the structural response depicted in Fig. 4.9. Moreover, it can be observed that the structural response results correspond to the findings of the Eigenvector analysis in Sec. 4.3.1. Figure 4.7 illustrates the strong coupling between the Short period mode, which is a longitudinal mode, and the first structural mode. The shape of the first structural mode, described in Sec. 4.1.1 and depicted in Fig. 4.1a, is characterised by the first bending mode with a torsional component. This mode is the same as the one detected in the X-Plane results shown in Figs. 4.11 and 4.12.

Figure 4.11: X-Plane Animation Results for Elevator Doublet Input with 10 Degrees at 2 Seconds

Figure 4.12: X-Plane Animation Results for Elevator Doublet Input with 10 Degrees at 3 Seconds

Elevator Chirp Input

In this simulation, the elevator command to excite the longitudinal motion is a chirp input with the following parameters: initial frequency $f_0 = 0.5 \text{ Hz}$, final frequency $f_f = 5 \text{ Hz}$, amplitude that is equivalent to 15° and duration time $t = 10 \text{ s}$. The final frequency of the chirp input was chosen to include the frequencies of the first five flexible modes. Figure 4.13 presents the longitudinal states response to the chirp input. Analogously to the previous section, the longitudinal states can be analysed. As shown in Fig. 4.13, as the input frequency increases, the response frequency of the longitudinal states correspondingly increases. This observation suggests that as the excitation frequency approaches or becomes nearly equivalent to the structural mode frequency, the dynamic response frequency increases. It is important to note that in this simulation the deflection input to the elevator begins at $t = 0 \text{ s}$. Therefore, the trimmed condition is not observed during the first second, as indicated by the longitudinal response in Fig. 4.8.

The structural response is illustrated in Fig. 4.14. The wing's deformation is shown in Fig. 4.14a, while the rotation is depicted in Fig. 4.14b. From these figures, it can be observed that the wing is reacting analogously to the schema explained in the previous simulation. Figures 4.14c and 4.14d show deformation and torsion of the horizontal tail tip. The vertical tail tip deformation and torsion are illustrated in Figs. 4.14e and 4.14f, respectively. Similarly to the previous simulation, the contributions of the horizontal tail and vertical tail are within a small range compared to the wing. However, for this simulation input, the horizontal tail and vertical tail tip deformation exhibited oscillatory behaviour. Specifically, from $t = 7.5 \text{ s}$ to $t = 9 \text{ s}$, the amplitude of the oscillations increased significantly. These high-amplitude oscillations could be attributed to the excitation of the fifth structural mode. The fifth mode, described in Sec. 4.1.1 and depicted in Fig. 4.1e, is characterised by a complex coupling between the first bending mode of the wing, the torsional motion of the wing, the engine motion, and the deformation of the fuselage, which consequently leads to the deformation of the tail. This mode has a frequency of 3.97 Hz . Therefore, it suggests that from $t = 7.5 \text{ s}$ to $t = 9 \text{ s}$, the frequency of the fifth structural mode is approached, resulting in high-amplitude oscillations in the aircraft tail. This conclusion is further supported by the eigenvector analysis in Sec. 4.3.1, which shows that the Short period, or the longitudinal motion, exhibits coupling not only with the first mode but also with the fifth mode.

Figure 4.13: F25/UPWing QS Longitudinal Response for Elevator Chirp Input

Figure 4.14: F25/UPWing QS Structural Response for Elevator Chirp Input

Fig. 4.15 presents the aircraft's response as obtained from X-Plane. This figure shows the aircraft response at $t = 0.94$ s, when the wing is deforming downward while twisting upward. By comparing this figure with the plots generated from MATLAB/Simulink, it can be concluded that the animation tool correctly depicts the structural response as shown in Figs. 4.14a and 4.14b. Moreover, as previously mentioned, the structural responses of the horizontal tail and vertical tail are within a smaller range compared to the wing response. Nevertheless, these tails exhibit oscillatory behavior, potentially due to the excitation of the fifth mode. This oscillatory deformation becomes particularly noticeable in the animation, especially for the time between $t = 7.5$ s and $t = 9$ s. To depict this behaviour, Fig. 4.16 shows the structural response of the horizontal tail at $t = 8.76$ s. At this moment, the horizontal tail deforms upward and rotates downward, as also observed in Figs. 4.14c and 4.14d. It is important to note that only for this simulation the deformation of the horizontal tail in Fig. 4.16 is multiplied by 3 to make it visible in the figures. Figure 4.17 also depicts the twist of the vertical tail, where the torsion values are multiplied by 10 for visibility. Although this contribution is small and barely recognisable in this figure, it can be observed in the animation video, due to the oscillatory behaviour.

Figure 4.15: X-Plane Animation Results for Elevator Chirp Input at 0.94 Second

Figure 4.16: X-Plane HE Animation Results for Elevator Chirp Input at 8.76 Seconds

Figure 4.17: X-Plane VE Animation Results for Elevator Chirp Input at 8.76 Seconds

4.3.3 Lateral Dynamics of Quasi-Steady Flexible Dynamics Model

Rudder Doublet Input

In this section, the lateral motion is excited by a rudder doublet input of 10 degrees. Figure 4.18 presents the lateral states response to this input. The lateral states response can be analysed analogue to Sec. 4.2.2. In Figure 4.18, the rudder deflection in the positive direction to the right, considering the aircraft from behind, generates a negative side force, leading to a positive yaw rate and a positive roll rate. As already explained in Sec. 4.2.2, the aircraft dynamics reveal a non-minimum phase response in the roll rate and bank angle with respect to the rudder deflection. This can also be observed in the quasi-steady flight dynamics simulation, as shown in Figs. 4.18c and 4.18d. The initial response of the bank angle and roll rate is negative for the first few seconds and then becomes positive. Furthermore, a deviation between the linear and non-linear system responses can be observed in Fig.4.18. This discrepancy arises because of the assumption made during linearisation of the system. This assumption asserts that the bank angle is sufficiently small, such that $\sin(\phi) \approx \phi$. However, this assumption becomes invalid when the dynamic system is excited with high amplitude inputs. To confirm this conclusion, a simulation was performed using a 1 degree rudder input. The results of this simulation are presented in the appendix in Fig. A.3. By comparing Fig. 4.18 with Fig. A.3, it can be concluded that for low amplitude inputs, the responses of the linear and non-linear systems are identical. In contrast, with higher excitation amplitudes, a noticeable deviation between the two systems is observed.

Figure 4.18: F25/UPWing QS Lateral Response for Rudder Doublet Input with 10 Degrees

Figure 4.19 represents the structural response of the wing tip for both sides. In this figure, the initial response, characterised by a negative roll rate and a negative bank angle (non-minimum phase effect), can also be observed. Specifically, the right wing deforms downward, while the left wing deforms upward due to the negative roll rate effect. This phenomenon occurs because the right wing experiences an induced downwash flow. This results in a decrease in the lift force (downward lift force), and a pitch-up moment. This reduction in the lift force leads to a downward deformation for the right wing, as shown in Fig. 4.19a. The same lifting force results in a moment that causes the right wing to twist upward, as illustrated in Fig. 4.19b. After this initial phase, the aircraft exhibits a positive roll rate and a positive yaw rate. With a positive roll rate, the right wing moves upward and twists downward due to the induced upwash flow. Additionally, positive yaw causes an increase in flow velocity over the left wing, producing more lift and resulting in upward deformation and downward twist. Therefore, the structural response of the wing exhibits an interaction due to the coupling effect of the roll and the yaw rate, as demonstrated in Figs. 4.19a and 4.19b.

The horizontal and vertical structural responses in this simulation show almost zero deformation and rotation. Therefore, the structural response analysis focuses solely on the wing. The structural response of the horizontal and vertical tails can be found in Fig. A.4 in the appendix.

It is important to note that after the first step of the rudder deflection, considering the initial lateral states response, the aircraft exhibits a negative roll moment in the first few seconds. Since the aircraft initially rolls to the left, the right wing experiences an upward lift force, leading to initial upward deformation and downward rotation of the right wing, with the left wing exhibiting the opposite behaviour. This occurs because of the roll moment. Subsequently, as the aircraft yaws positively, the left wing experiences an increase in lift force, deforming upward and causing a pitch-down moment, resulting in downward rotation. Then, the wing response reflects the combined effects of roll rate and yaw rate, as explained earlier. Figure 4.19 directly shows the reaction of the wing to the yaw rate and the roll rate, whereas the initial reactions to the roll moment and the yaw moment are not immediately apparent. This could be due to the negligible effect of the derivatives $C_{l\delta ail}$, $C_{n\delta ail}$, $C_{l\delta r}$ and $C_{n\delta r}$ compared to the stability derivatives C_{lp} and C_{nr} on the wing deformation. To confirm this effect, a stability derivative analysis should be performed. However, this is beyond the scope of this work. Therefore, the structural response analysis for lateral motion simulation assumes that the wing responds directly to the effects of roll and yaw rate without initially showing the effects of the roll and yaw moment resulting from the rudder deflection or the aileron deflection in later simulations.

Figure 4.19: F25/UPWing QS Wing Structural Response for Rudder Doublet Input with 10 Degrees

Figures 4.20, 4.21, and 4.22 represent the animation results from X-Plane. Figure 4.20 shows the animation result at $t = 2.5$ s, where the right wing deforms upward and twists downward at the tip, while the left wing also deforms upward and twists downward, but to a minor extent than the right wing. Comparing Fig. 4.20 with Fig. 4.19, it can be concluded that the animation tool reflects the same results as depicted in the MATLAB/Simulink plots. Furthermore, in Fig. 4.19, it can be observed that at approximately $t = 3.76$ s, the deformation and twist of the wing reaches the minimum and is close to zero. This observation is also consistent with the animation results shown in Fig. 4.21. Figure 4.22 shows the response of the aircraft at $t = 4.5$ s. At this moment, the tip of the left and the right wing deforms upward and rotates downward. However, the deformation of the left wing is higher pronounced than that of the right wing. By comparing Figs. 4.22 and 4.19, it can be concluded that the animation results correspond to the MATLAB/Simulink simulation results. Furthermore, the eigenvector analysis described in Sec. 4.3.1 reveals that the Dutch roll motion (typically excited by a rudder input) exhibits coupling to the second structural mode. The shape of this mode is described in Sec. 4.1.1 and illustrated in Fig. 4.1b. This shape is characterised by asymmetric wing bending, which can be observed in the X-Plane animation results. This demonstrates that the animation tool is capable of visualising not only symmetric deformations, as shown in the previous simulation, but also asymmetric deformations, as illustrated in this simulation.

Figure 4.20: X-Plane Animation Results for Rudder Doublet Input with 10 Degrees at 2.5 Seconds

Figure 4.21: X-Plane Animation Results for Rudder Doublet Input with 10 Degrees at 3.76 Seconds

Figure 4.22: X-Plane Animation Results for Rudder Doublet Input with 10 Degrees at 4.5 Seconds

Aileron Doublet Input

This simulation excites the lateral motion using a doublet input in the aileron with a deflection of 15 degrees. Figure 4.23 illustrate the lateral states response to this input. A positive aileron deflection implies that the right aileron deflects downward and the left aileron deflects upward, considering the aircraft from behind. The downward deflection of the right aileron generates an upward lift force, while the upward deflection of the left aileron generates a downward lift force. These opposing lift forces create a negative roll moment, resulting in a negative roll rate and subsequently a negative bank angle, as depicted in Figs. 4.23b and 4.23a, respectively. The combined side force induced by the roll rate leads to a negative yaw moment, which causes a negative yaw rate, as shown in Fig. 4.23d. As a result of the negative yaw rate, the sideslip angle and the heading angle decrease. The response of the sideslip angle and the heading angle can be obtained from Figs. 4.23e and 4.23c, respectively. Moreover, the coupling between the roll and the Dutch roll motion can be observed in Figs. 4.23a and 4.23b. In these figures, the response to the doublet input is depicted during the first 3 seconds, followed by the Dutch roll oscillations. Furthermore, similar to the previous simulation, the deviation between the linear and non-linear system responses can be observed. The explanation for this discrepancy from the previous simulation applies to this simulation as well.

Figure 4.23: F25/UPWing QS Lateral Response for Aileron Doublet Input with 15 Degrees

Figure 4.24 illustrates the wing tip response to the above mentioned aileron input. Similarly to the simulation with rudder input, the wing structural response here directly represents the effect of the roll rate. Due to the negative roll rate resulting from the first step, the left wing experiences an upwash. This upward flow causes the left wing to deform upward and twist downward, as depicted in Figs. 4.24a and 4.24b, respectively. Meanwhile, the right wing deforms significantly downward and twists upward until it nearly reaches a twist angle of zero. Following the second step, the positive roll rate causes the left and right wings to behave in an opposite way. Afterwards, the wing deformation response reflects the Dutch roll component in the Roll motion.

The structural response contribution of the horizontal and vertical tails is negligible compared to that of the wing. Therefore, the structural response analysis is focused on the wings. However, the response of the tail structure is also depicted in the appendix in Fig. A.5 as a reference.

Figure 4.24: F25/UPWing QS Wing Structural Response for Aileron Doublet Input with 15 Degrees

Figure 4.25 represents the aircraft's response after the first positive step input to the aileron at $t = 1.8$ s. As observed, the right aileron deflects downwards and the left aileron deflects upward, resulting in negative rolling. Figure 4.25a shows the front view of the aircraft, where the left wing deforms upward and twists downward, while the right wing exhibits a twist angle of almost zero and a small deformation. This asymmetric behaviour is also evident in the back view, as illustrated in Fig. 4.25b. The aircraft response is presented from different perspectives to clearly show the aileron deflection in Fig. 4.25a and the asymmetric behaviour in Fig. 4.25b. Figure 4.26 presents the response of the aircraft after the second step input at $t = 2.8$ s. From the front view, as shown in Fig. 4.26a, the aileron deflection can be observed. The back view, in Fig. 4.26b, also reveals the asymmetric response of the wing: the left wing deforms and twists within a small range, while the right wing deflects significantly upwards and twists downwards. For this simulation, it can also be concluded that Figs. 4.25 and 4.26 represent the MATLAB/Simulink results as presented in Fig. 4.24. Furthermore, the conclusions from the eigenvector analysis, explained in Sec. 4.3.1, align also with the X-Plane animation results. The eigenvector analysis reveals that the Roll motion is coupled with the second

structural mode, characterised by asymmetric wing bending. This mode shape is clearly detected in the animation results, as shown in Figs. 4.25 and 4.26.

(a) Front View

(b) Back View

Figure 4.25: X-Plane Animation Results for Aileron Doublet Input with 15 Degrees at 1.8 Seconds

(a) Front View

(b) Back View

Figure 4.26: X-Plane Animation Results for Aileron Doublet Input with 15 Degrees at 2.8 Seconds

Aileron Step Input

This simulation presents an excitation of the lateral motion with a step input in the aileron of 1 degree. Figure 4.27 shows the response of the lateral states. The deflection of the aileron is negative, resulting in a positive roll rate, a positive bank angle, a positive yaw rate, a positive heading angle, and a positive sideslip angle.

Figure 4.28 illustrates the structural response of the wing to the negative step input to the aileron. The effect of the positive roll rate can be observed, as the right wing experiences an upwash. This leads to an increase in the lift force on the right wing that deforms the wing upward in the z direction, as shown in Fig. 4.28a. This force also generates a moment that rotates the right wing downward around the y -axis, as depicted in Fig. 4.28b. In contrast, the left wing experiences a downwash. As a result, the lift force decreases on the left wing, which deforms it downwards and rotates the wing upward.

The structural response contribution of the horizontal and vertical tails is negligible compared to that of the wing. Consequently, the structural response analysis is primarily focused on the wings. However, the response of the tail structure is also shown in the appendix in Fig. A.6 for reference.

Figure 4.29 represents an example of the animation results of X-Plane. This figure depicts the aircraft response at $t = 2.5 s$. The figure demonstrates that with a negative aileron deflection, the left aileron deflects downward while the right aileron deflects upward. Due to the effect of the roll rate, the right wing deforms upward and rotates downward, while the left wing exhibits the opposite behaviour. Comparing Fig. 4.29 with Fig. 4.28, it can be concluded that the animation results show the asymmetric bending observed in the MATLAB/Simulink simulation results. It is important to note that only for this simulation the deformation of the wing in Fig. 4.29 has been multiplied by 2 for visualisation purposes. Analogous to the previous simulation, the asymmetric bending detected in the animation results is consistent with the eigenvector analysis.

Figure 4.27: F25/UPWing QS Lateral Response for Aileron Step Input with 1 Degree

Figure 4.28: F25/UPWing QS Wing Structural Response for Aileron Step Input with 1 Degree

Figure 4.29: X-Plane Animation Results for Aileron Step Input with 1 Degree at 2.5 Seconds

4.4 Unsteady Flexible Flight Dynamics Simulations

In this section, the results of the unsteady flight dynamics simulation are presented. As mentioned in the introduction of this chapter, the tool used for calculating the unsteady flight dynamics model requires approximately 30 minutes to compute the dynamics including only the first five aeroelastic modes. This computational demand makes real-time simulation and animation in X-Plane impractical. Instead, the results are analysed by comparing them to the rigid body and quasi-steady flight dynamics responses. The comparisons are based on the response of the longitudinal and the lateral states and their corresponding structural responses. The simulations are performed according to the methodology explained in Chapter 3.1.3. Table 4.6 illustrates the studies executed to excite the longitudinal and lateral motions. An elevator doublet is used as input to excite the longitudinal motion, while the lateral motion is excited using a doublet on the rudder.

Table 4.6: Time-Domain Simulations for the Unsteady Flexible Flight Dynamics Model

Motion	Input	Control Surface
Longitudinal	Doublet 5°	Elevator
Lateral	Doublet 5°	Rudder

4.4.1 Longitudinal Dynamics of Unsteady Flexible Dynamics Model

In this section, the longitudinal motion is excited with an elevator doublet of 5 degrees. The response of the aircraft is analysed analogously to the previous simulations executed for the rigid-body and quasi-steady models. Figure 4.30 depicts the longitudinal states response for the rigid body, quasi-steady, and unsteady flight dynamics models. From this figure, it can be concluded that the longitudinal state responses for the quasi-steady and unsteady models are almost identical, except for the velocity response. In the quasi-steady model, the velocity response for the second step of the elevator decreases significantly more than in the unsteady model. Figure 4.30c also illustrates the different trim values of alpha for the rigid body and the flexible models, as also indicated in Tab. 4.3.

Figure 4.31 depicts the response of the right wing tip to the same elevator input. It can be concluded that the wing response is the same for both the quasi-steady and unsteady models. Moreover, the highest wing tip deformation for both flexible models is around 12 %. Similarly to the structural response of the wing, the structural responses of the horizontal and vertical tail show no deviation between the quasi-steady and unsteady approaches and are illustrated in the appendix in Fig. A.7 for reference.

Figure 4.30: F25/UPWing US Longitudinal Response for Elevator Doublet Input with 5 Degrees

Figure 4.31: F25/UPWing US Right Wing Structural Response for Elevator Doublet Input with 5 Degrees

4.4.2 Lateral Dynamics of Unsteady Flexible Dynamics Model

The lateral motion is excited with a rudder doublet of 5 degrees. Figure 4.32 illustrates the lateral state responses. Similar to the longitudinal state responses, it is evident that the quasi-steady and unsteady approaches exhibit the same behavior. However, notable deviations can be observed in Figs. 4.32c and 4.32d between the flexible and rigid body responses. In this simulation, the bank angle and roll rate for the flexible model show higher amplitudes than those of the rigid body model.

Figure 4.33 shows the wing structural response to the same input. As observed from this figure, the structural response of the wing shows no deviation between the two different aerodynamic models. The structural response of the wing for both flexible models varies between approximately 4 % and 7.5 %. The horizontal and vertical tail structural responses reveal also no deviation for the quasi-steady and unsteady models and are depicted in the appendix in Fig. A.8.

Figure 4.32: F25/UPWing US Lateral Response for Rudder Doublet Input with 5 Degrees

Figure 4.33: F25/UPWing US Right Wing Structural Response for Rudder Doublet Input with 5 Degrees

5 | Conclusion

This work aimed to develop and implement a real-time animation tool to visualise the deformation of a flexible aircraft. The main objectives were to design a robust framework, ensure an accurate representation of wing, horizontal tail, and vertical tail deformations, and evaluate the tool's performance under various simulated conditions.

The methodology for developing this tool involved three main components: calculating and simulating the aeroelastic flight dynamics model in MATLAB/Simulink, animating the model in X-Plane, and implementing a plugin to facilitate communication between Simulink and X-Plane. Simulating the aeroelastic flight dynamics model begins with calculating rigid body stability derivatives using AVL, followed by extracting eigenvalues and eigenvectors of each structural mode from NASTRAN. These data are then used to calculate the flight dynamics model of a flexible aircraft in MATLAB, which is subsequently simulated in Simulink. For the animation part, the X-Plane online flight simulator is used to fly and animate a customised aircraft. Since the aircraft model used in this thesis was similar to the Airbus A321 neo, a A320 model was used and extensively modified in Blender, including rigging and animating the model. Additionally, the "xplane2blender" add-on was installed in Blender to export the 3-D model to an ".obj" file, that is compatible with X-Plane. Finally, a plug-in was implemented in C++ to enable communication between Simulink and X-Plane. This plug-in can disable X-Plane's physics engine and allow it to receive data from Simulink. To ensure real-time animation, the plug-in was implemented using the connectionless communication protocol UDP.

The tool developed in this work was applied to the UP-Wing demonstrator aircraft model, which is a flexible aircraft with a high aspect ratio, making it ideal for testing the animation tool. The aeroelastic models in this study were calculated using two aerodynamic approaches: quasi-steady and unsteady. However, due to the extensive computation time required for the unsteady configuration, the animation tool was only used to analyse the aircraft's dynamics for the quasi-steady approach.

In this study, the investigation begins with a stability analysis for the UP-Wing demonstrator aircraft, by examining the zero-map. It was concluded that the aircraft is stable for the three aerodynamic approaches considered in this work: Rigid body, quasi-steady and unsteady. The examination also included a comparison of the frequency and damping of the elastic modes for both quasi-steady and unsteady models. For modes 1, 2, 4, and 5, the deviations in frequencies and damping were minimal. However, mode 3 exhibited a higher frequency and higher damping in the quasi-steady approach than in the unsteady model. The same comparison was conducted for the rigid body modes, showing nearly zero deviation between the three aerodynamic models. Notable deviations were observed in

the Short Period and Spiral modes when comparing their frequency and damping between the rigid body approach and the two flexible dynamics models. Furthermore, the comparison was also extended to include the trim values of the aircraft. The trim values of the quasi-steady and unsteady models were almost identical. However, as expected, the angle of attack required to trim a flexible aircraft was higher than that required for a rigid body. This increase in the angle of attack resulted in higher induced drag, which required greater thrust for compensation. Consequently, a deviation in thrust values was observed between the rigid body and the two flexible dynamics models. However, the discrepancy in thrust values between the quasi-steady and unsteady models was unpredictable and could not be explained, indicating that the quasi-steady flight dynamics model requires further review.

The evaluation of the quasi-steady flight dynamics model included an eigenvector analysis and time-domain simulations for both longitudinal and lateral motions. For the eigenvector analysis, it was concluded that the Short period mode is coupled with the first and fifth structural modes, while the Phugoid mode is not coupled with any of the structural modes. For the lateral motion, the Dutch roll and Roll motion exhibit a strong coupling with the second and fourth elastic modes. Regarding the time-domain simulations for the longitudinal motion, the aircraft was simulated using two different inputs: a doublet input and a chirp input. It was observed that the contribution of the tail's structural response was nearly zero for both simulations. However, for the chirp input, the response exhibited oscillatory behaviour. Although the tail's contribution was minimal, it was noticeable in the animation results for the chirp input because of the oscillatory nature of the response. Additionally, the wing's response to elevator inputs showed a phase shift, which could be verified by analysing the Bode diagram. Furthermore, it was concluded that the results of the time-domain simulations corresponded to the finding of the eigenvector analysis. As in the structure response, the shapes of the first and fifth elastic modes were detected. Moreover, for the lateral motion investigation, three time-domain simulations were conducted: a rudder doublet input, an aileron doublet input, and an aileron step input. The dynamic response of the lateral motion exhibited a non-minimum phase effect, evident in the roll rate and bank angle responses to the rudder input. This effect was also observed in the structural response of the quasi-steady model. In addition, a strong coupling was identified between roll and yaw rate in the structural response. Furthermore, for all lateral motion simulations, it was detected that the horizontal and vertical tail structural response are nearly zero compared to that of the wing. Consequently, the analysis for the lateral structure response focused mainly on the wing. It was observed that the wing structural response did not directly show the effects of roll or yaw moments, but rather the subsequent effects of roll rate and yaw rate. In addition, the lateral time-domain simulation results were aligned with the conclusion of the eigenvector analysis, since the second and fourth elastic modes were observed in the structural response.

Another important observation from the quasi-steady simulations was the discrepancy between the states response of linear and non-linear systems during lateral excitation, which did not appear in the longitudinal states. Upon investigating this phenomenon, it was concluded that the identity of linear and non-linear state responses for longitudinal motion is independent of the input value. However, for the lateral motion, increasing the input value leads to a greater deviation between linear and non-linear

states response. This discrepancy arises due to the assumption made in the linearisation calculation. The assumption asserts that the bank angle is very small, so that $\sin(\phi)$ is approximately equal to the angle itself. Therefore, this assumption is invalid for large input values.

The main focus of this study was to compare the simulation results from MATLAB/Simulink with the animation results from X-Plane. This comparison demonstrated that the animation tool successfully displayed the results shown in the MATLAB plots. To ensure the tool's reliability, images of the animation at different time steps were compared to the corresponding time steps in the MATLAB plots. This process was performed for various simulations, confirming that the tool accurately displayed the data sent from Simulink to X-Plane. The animation tool displayed the deformation and torsion of the wing, the horizontal tail, and the vertical tail. Additionally, the comparison showed that the rigging and animation strategy used to create the 3-D model enabled the tool to display complex structural modes, particularly those involving coupling between bending and torsion. The animation tool could display non-linear deformation and torsion and could animate both symmetric and asymmetric structural modes. Moreover, the X-Plane animation results confirmed the findings from the eigenvector analysis, due to the fact that the shape of the first and fifth modes were observed while exciting the longitudinal motion and the second and fourth were detected while exciting the lateral motion.

Furthermore, the aircraft response based on the unsteady flight dynamics model was also analysed. The analysis compared the rigid body, quasi-steady, and unsteady aerodynamic models. This investigation included two time-domain simulations: one for longitudinal motion and the other for lateral motion. The states and structural response of the quasi-steady and unsteady models were observed to be almost identical for the simulations executed. Similarly to the quasi-steady model, the tail structural response in the unsteady model was nearly zero compared to the wing contribution. In addition, a small deviation was noticed when comparing the rigid body with the two flexible dynamics for both longitudinal and lateral motions.

In conclusion, this thesis presents the development of a tool for the real-time animation of flexible aircraft, with a specific focus on the deformation and rotation of the lift surfaces. The tool is capable of visualising the dynamic behaviours of flexible aircraft and has several potential applications. It allows testing of various design elements related to aircraft flexibility, such as controllers or new wing designs. The updated model can be evaluated directly using an online flexible simulator before performing real flight tests. This process not only reduces costs, but also enhances safety by enabling comprehensive testing and analysis within a virtual environment. In addition, the tool can serve educational purposes, helping students understand and visualise the behaviour of flexible aircraft during flight. Furthermore, a significant advantage of this tool is its applicability to any aircraft.

5.1 Outlook and Future Work

Future work for this thesis could focus on two main points. First, optimising the implementation strategies of the quasi-steady and unsteady flight dynamics models to reduce computational time. This improvement would enable the animation tool to animate any number of modes. Additionally, the quasi-steady model should be reviewed to ensure that the thrust values between the quasi-steady and unsteady models are identical. Further investigation of stability derivatives for the quasi-steady model could be performed to ensure the validity of the structural response during lateral motion. Moreover, the assumption in linearisation that the bank angle is very small could be eliminated, making the flight dynamics model valid regardless of input values. The second point concerns the animation part. In this work, the animation focused on the wing, horizontal tail, and vertical tail. Future work could extend this to include the deformation of the fuselage and engine. Additionally, the animation of the 3-D model currently displays bending and torsion movements; this could be optimised to include translational movement of the wing in the x-y plane.

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A | Appendix

Figure A.1: Wing and Tail of F25/UPWing in AVL from Top the View

Table A.1: F25/UPWing First Five Elastic Modes

Mode no.	ω_n [Hz]	Mode Shape
1	2.31	Symmetric first wing bending with a minor torsional component
2	2.76	Asymmetric second wing bending with a small torsional influence
3	3.19	Symmetric first wing bending, wing torsion, engine bending and fuselage bending
4	3.46	Asymmetric second wing bending, wing torsion and fuselage torsion
5	3.97	Symmetric first wing bending, fuselage bending and engine torsion

Table A.2: Aerodynamic Stability Derivatives Resulting from AVL

	C_L	C_D	C_Y	C_l	C_m	C_n
0	0.4014	0	0	0	0.0883	0
α	0.1244	0	0	0	-0.1019	0
β	0	0	-0.009	-0.0038	0	0.0035
p	0	0	-0.1795	-0.5861	0	-0.0013
q	22.3335	0	0	0	-91.2509	0
r	0	0	0.5152	0.1452	0	-0.2209

Table A.3: Control Surface Stability Derivatives Resulting from AVL

	$C_{L\delta}$	$C_{D\delta}$	$C_{Y\delta}$	$C_{l\delta}$	$C_{m\delta}$	$C_{n\delta}$
δ_e	0.0115	0	0	0	-0.0696	0
δ_{ail1r}	0.0039	0	-2.8E-04	-0.0011	-0.0046	-1E-05
δ_{ail1l}	0.0039	0	2.8E-04	0.0011	-0.0046	1E-05
δ_{ail2r}	0.0027	0	-2.12E-04	-9.6E-04	-0.0040	-3E-06
δ_{ail2l}	0.0027	0	2.12E-04	9.6E-04	-0.0040	3E-06
$\delta_{outerflap_r}$	0.0081	0	-4.39E-04	-0.0015	-0.0069	-7.6E-05
$\delta_{outerflap_l}$	0.0081	0	4.39E-04	0.0015	-0.0069	7.6E-05
$\delta_{flaperon_r}$	0.0032	0	-1.06E-04	-3.79E-04	-2.6E-04	-6.6E-05
$\delta_{flaperon_l}$	0.0032	0	1.06E-04	3.79E-04	-2.6E-04	6.6E-05
$\delta_{innerflap_r}$	0.0049	0	-1.03E-04	-3.75E-04	0.0048	-1.33E-04
$\delta_{innerflap_l}$	0.0047	0	1.01E-04	3.65E-04	0.0047	1.28E-04
δ_r	0	0	-0.0069	-7.14E-04	0	0.0033

Figure A.2: Pole-Zero Map Rudder Command to Roll Rate (RB)

(a) Heading Angle Response

(b) Yaw Rate Response

(c) Bank Angle Response

(d) Roll Rate Response

(e) Sideslip Angle Response

(f) Rudder Input

Figure A.3: F25/UPWing QS Lateral Response for Rudder Doublet Input with 1 Degree

(a) Horizontal Tail Deformation Response

(b) Horizontal Tail Torsion Response

(c) Vertical Tail Deformation Response

(d) Vertical Tail Torsion Response

Figure A.4: F25/UPWing QS Tail Structural Response for Rudder Doublet Input with 10 Degree

(a) Horizontal Tail Deformation Response

(b) Horizontal Tail Torsion Response

(c) Vertical Tail Deformation Response

(d) Vertical Tail Torsion Response

Figure A.5: F25/UPWing QS Tail Structural Response for Aileron Doublet Input with 15 Degree

(a) Horizontal Tail Deformation Response

(b) Horizontal Tail Torsion Response

(c) Vertical Tail Deformation Response

(d) Vertical Tail Torsion Response

Figure A.6: F25/UPWing QS Tail Structural Response for Aileron Step Input with 1 Degree

Figure A.7: F25/UPWing US Tail Structural Response for Elevator Doublet Input with 5 Degrees

Figure A.8: F25/UPWing US Tail Structural Response for Rudder Doublet Input with 5 Degrees